

ReNEW

D1.1- Resilience and Sustainability analysis
in IWT and strategic development Baseline
Building Blocks v1

Funded by
the European Union

Document Info

Document

Title	Resilience-centric Smart, Green, Networked EU Inland Waterways
Acronym	ReNEW
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01
Type of Action	HORIZON-IA
Grant Number	101069682
Start date	1 September 2022
Duration	36 months
Document identifier	D1.1- Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v1
Due Date of Delivery to EC	30-04-2023
Actual Date of Delivery to EC	28-04-2023
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Work package	WP1 - Methodology for EU Resilient and Sustainable IWT Infrastructure System
Lead Beneficiary	Institute of Shipping Economics and Logistics (ISL)

Contributor(s)

Main Contributor(s)	Marija Jović - ISL Wiebke Duhme – ISL
Contributor(s) (alphabetical order)	Alexandra Micu - RDS Mauro Carolli - SER Mostepha Khouadjia - IRTX Rainer Müller - ISL Ramdane Tami -- IRTX

Control Sheet			
Version	Date	Editor	Summary of Modifications
0.1	14.02.2023	Wiebke Duhme	Integration and structuring of text passages from working document.
0.2	20.02.2023	Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Hazards and vulnerability scenario catalogue
0.3	27.02.2023	Marija Jović	KPIs for resilience and sustainability
0.3	06.03.2023	Marija Jović	Update of references, introduction categories for threats and hazards
0.3	07.03.2023	Wiebke Duhme	Revision CBA
0.3	08.03.2023	Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Other KPIs description; revision threats and hazards;
0.3	09.03.2023	Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Introduction building blocks
0.3		Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Deliverable structure and methodology
0.3	10.03.2023	Ramdane Tami	Revision of the document
0.3	10.03.2023	Mostepha Khouadjia	Revision of the document
0.3	12.03.2023	Ramdane Tami Ramdane Tami	Additional building blocks and data sources
0.3	12.03.2023	Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Executive Summary
0.3	15.03.2023	Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Table “mapping the ReNEW output”
0.3	15.03.2023	Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Conclusion and further steps
0.3	16.03.2023	Wiebke Duhme	Final Revision
0.3	16.03.2023	Marija Jović	Final Revision
0.3	20.03.2023	Mauro Carolli	Revision, comments
0.3	30.03.2023	Alexandra Micu	Revision, comments
0.4	12.04.2023	Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Corrections based on partner’s feedback
0.5	17.04.2023	Wiebke Duhme	Minor corrections, revision
0.5	26.04.2023	Rainer Müller	Minor corrections, revision
Final	27.04.2023	Marija Jović, Wiebke Duhme	Layout check, completion of final version

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

The authors, reviewers, and contributors participating in the ReNEW Consortium took all the necessary measures and in good faith to provide the information in the most accurate, consistent, and lawful manner. However, neither the ReNEW consortium, its members nor any party mentioned here above shall not be responsible or liable for any errors or omissions in the content of this document or for any type of losses, damages or costs resulting from the use of the data mentioned in this document.

Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
BIVAS	Binnenvaart Analyse Systeem
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CESNI	European Committee for drawing up standards in the field of inland navigation
CISA	Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency
DOS	Denial of Service
DT	Data Base
EC	European Commission
ECDIS	Inland Electronic Chart Display Information Service,
EEA	European Environment Agency
ENC	Electronic Navigational Charts
ERI	Electronic Ship Reporting,
FPM	Floating Modular Platform
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographic Information System
HALEM	Hydrodynamic Algorithm for Logistic Enhancement, Module
HEC-HMS	Hydrologic Modelling System
HiPIMS	Standards for High-Performance Integrated hydrodynamic Modelling System
iRIC	International River Interface Cooperative
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
IT	Information Technology
IW	Inland Waterways
IW-NET	Innovation-driven Collaborative European Inland Waterways Transport Network
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LL	Living Lab
NPV	Net Present Value
NSW	National Single Window
NtS	Notices to Skippers
OpenCLSim	Open source Complex Logistics Simulation
PP	Payback Period
QGIS	Quantum Geographic Information System
RBMP	River Basin Management Plans
ReNEW	Resilience-centric Smart, Green, Networked EU Inland Waterways
RIS	River Information Services

RIS-COMEX	RIS enabled Corridor Management Execution
RSQF	Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
VNF	Voies navigables de France
VTT	Vessel Tracking and Tracing
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WISE	Water Information System for Europe
WSV	Deutsche Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes

Table of Contents

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	1
2 INTRODUCTION	2
2.1 OBJECTIVES	3
2.2 DELIVERABLE STRUCTURE AND GENERAL METHODOLOGY	4
2.3 MAPPING THE RENEW OUTPUT	5
3 HAZARDS AND VULNERABILITIES SCENARIO CATALOGUE	8
3.1 DEFINITIONS	8
3.2 SCENARIO CATALOGUE – VERSION 1	13
3.2.1 LABOUR-ORIENTED / PANDEMIC	15
3.2.2 NATURAL PHENOMENON DISRUPTION EVENTS	19
3.2.3 CRIME AND CYBER ATTACKS	33
3.2.4 OPERATIONAL DISRUPTION EVENTS	39
3.2.5 OTHER DISRUPTION EVENTS	50
4 ACHIEVING RESILIENCE AND SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH PROPER KPIS AND COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS	53
4.1 BACKGROUND/OVERVIEW	53
4.2 SUSTAINABILITY, RESILIENCE AND DISRUPTION PHASES	53
4.3 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS	56
4.3.1 SUSTAINABILITY KPIS, METRICS AND MEASURES	58
4.3.2 RESILIENCE KPIS, METRICS AND MEASURES	60
4.3.3 OTHER KPIS	65
4.3.4 FIRST SELECTION OF KPIS RELEVANT FOR THE RENEW LIVING LABS	67
4.4 COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS	69
5 BUILDING BLOCKS AND DATA SOURCES	74
5.1 BUILDING BLOCKS	74
5.1.1 ANALYSES/CATALOGUES	75
5.1.2 AI BASED MODELS	75
5.1.3 METHODOLOGY	75
5.1.4 MODELS	76
5.1.5 SIMULATION BASED MODELS	76
5.1.6 TOOLS	78
5.1.7 VESSEL ROUTE PLANNER	78
5.2 DATA SOURCES	79
5.2.1 CLIMATE AND ENVIRONMENTAL DATA	79

5.2.2	DATABASES	80
5.2.3	MARITIME AIS DATA	80
5.2.4	WATERWAYS AND INFRASTRUCTURE INFORMATION	81
5.2.5	OTHER DATA SOURCES	82
6	CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER STEPS	83
7	REFERENCES	84

List of Tables

TABLE 1:	ADHERENCE TO RENEW'S GA DELIVERABLE & TASKS DESCRIPTIONS	5
TABLE 2:	OVERVIEW OF LABOUR-ORIENTED/PANDEMIC DISRUPTION EVENTS	15
TABLE 3:	OVERVIEW OF NATURAL PHENOMENON DISRUPTION EVENTS	19
TABLE 4:	OVERVIEW OF CRIME AND CYBER ATTACKS	33
TABLE 5:	OVERVIEW OF OPERATIONAL DISRUPTION EVENTS	39
TABLE 6:	OVERVIEW OF OTHER DISRUPTION EVENTS - BUREAUCRACY	50
TABLE 7:	OVERVIEW OF OTHER DISRUPTION EVENTS - ECONOMICAL/REGULATORY	50
TABLE 8:	OVERVIEW OF BUILDING BLOCKS	74
TABLE 9:	OVERVIEW OF DATA SOURCES	79

List of Figures

FIGURE 1:	EXTRACT FROM MIRO WHITEBOARD, TOOLS FOR ASSESSMENT	14
FIGURE 2:	EXAMPLE FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF AN EVENT	14
FIGURE 3:	RESILIENCE AS A COMPONENT OF SUSTAINABILITY	54
FIGURE 4:	SUPPLY CHAIN RESILIENCE PHASES (AUTHOR BASED ON SHEFFI 2007)	55
FIGURE 5:	RESEARCH STEPS	57
FIGURE 6:	SIMPLE EXAMPLE OF A RISK MATRIX	83

1 Executive Summary

ReNEW is the acronym for the project "Resilience-centric Smart, Green, Networked EU Inland Waterways". This project is funded by the European Commission under the topic "HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-09 "Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways".

The key objective of this deliverable is to create a hazards and vulnerabilities scenarios catalogue, to give an overview of resilience and sustainability Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA), and to identify building blocks and data sources serving as baselines for the development of new solutions. Considering that this is the first version of the deliverable (there are three versions in total), and the information has the status of the 1st release, this is a dynamic document where the information will be further analysed and concretized.

The Hazards and Vulnerabilities scenarios catalogue contains various identified threats, hazards, vulnerabilities and risks which are classified into 5 categories: Labour oriented/Pandemic, natural phenomenon events (e.g., low and high-water periods, ice), crime, and cyber-attacks, operational disruption events, and other disruption events. The catalogue was created based on known threats that happened in the past, and on possible threats which could appear in the future. In addition, the catalogue contains the description of potential direct and indirect consequences related to identified threats, hazards, risks and vulnerabilities.

In total, 57 hazards and threats have been identified and the project partners responsible for the LL assessed the aforementioned events (threats and hazards) according to the relevance, the impact strength, and the likelihood of occurrence. The catalogue serves as a baseline in order to better determine the scope for the ReNEW Living Lab (LL) use cases and for the later development of what-if-scenarios.

The next step was to define KPIs and related metrics and measures in the context of resilience and sustainability. In this version of the deliverable, the overview of various resilience and sustainability KPIs is provided. The KPIs were also assessed according to importance by LLs (however, at this stage the KPIs could not be assessed in detail). Furthermore, this deliverable contains the theoretical framework of CBA and possible implementation within the framework of ReNEW. At present, no information is available on the costs and benefits for ReNEW, so as a first step only a theoretical consideration of a CBA and a presentation of the proposed approach is given here. In the case of ReNEW, it is assumed that an investment is only a kind of insurance to improve resilience with regard to any damage that may occur. As a result, the costs that arise in the event of damage are examined. The measures to improve resilience should limit the damage at a low level or, in the best case, prevent the occurring at all. These reduced/eliminated damage costs are then classified as benefits.

In the last part of the deliverable, the initial selection of building blocks and data sources that may be relevant to the ReNEW LLs is provided. These will be deepened and elaborated during the next phases of the project and adapted to the needs of the LLs.

2 Introduction

Inland waterway transportation is considered to play an important role in the decarbonisation and reducing the congestion of the transport sector and consolidate economic development. However, events such as low- or high-water periods can cause potentially long-term disruptions of the respective transport chains.

The main objective of ReNEW is to identify ways to balance the quest towards more sustainability and resilience in inland waterway transportation. As described in the Grant Agreement (GA) this will be carried out by developing decision support tools for strategic planning and operational optimization of inland waterway transport chains, taking resilience and sustainability into account. Innovative solutions fostering the resilience and sustainability of inland waterway infrastructure will be developed and Information Technology (IT) tools such as "green resilient Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) dataspace" and "digital twins" will be implemented in order to enable efficient data exchange between all stakeholders involved.

The ReNEW results are tested and demonstrated in 4 Living Labs:

- Living Lab #1 – Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchromodality City Logistics Hub
- Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway management – DIW2024
- Living Lab #3 – Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, in addition, to boosting modal shift
- Living Lab #4 – Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

This document is the first deliverable of WP1 – “Methodology for EU Resilient and Sustainable IWT Infrastructure System” and is foreseen as the first contribution for Task 1.1 – “Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks”.

Under WP1, in support of the vision of a resilient and sustainable infrastructure system for inland navigation, a value-based analysis will be undertaken to ensure IWT's adaptation to climate change while maintaining competitiveness. The main aim of WP1 is the development of the ReNEW methodological framework for resilient and sustainable green IWT strategy planning, as well as the establishment of a framework of tools and solutions for analyzing infrastructure interdependencies and safety risks, reconfiguring transportation services, and determining the impact of natural or man-made disasters on the IW ecological environment.

Within Task 1.1 building blocks will be provided that serve as a basis for the planning, operation, and evaluation of new solutions (e.g., autonomous barges), for the digital twins, and for the evaluation and benchmarking of emission-neutral solutions. These building blocks will be tested in the LL scenarios.

Task 1.1. consists of 4 subtasks, which are only outlined below. The detailed description based on the GA can be found in Table 1.

- ST1.1.1 Hazards and vulnerabilities in IW Transport
- ST1.1.2 Models and tools and related data sources for IW Hazards and Vulnerabilities
- ST1.1.3 Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF), KPIs, and metrics.
- ST1.1.4 Resilience and Agility strategies

2.1 Objectives

According to the GA, the description of the deliverable D1.1 Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v1 is the following: “Hazards and vulnerability scenario catalogue, and resilience and sustainability KPIs and cost benefit analysis, data sources 1st release”.

In this respect, one of the main objectives of this deliverable will be to give a comprehensive overview of threats and hazards that might affect IWT, description of vulnerabilities as well and the consequences of disruption, both direct and indirect. Another objective is the identification of resilience and sustainability KPIs, the preparation of a cost benefit analysis and to provide a set of building blocks that might be of relevance for ReNEW.

Against this background and in line with the description of the subtasks of Task 1.1, this deliverable will define risks and hazards to IWT and identify, profile and catalogue factors like extreme climate events, technical and human failures, physical and cyber threats and infrastructural bottlenecks in IWT. The result will be a hazard and vulnerability scenario catalogue based on known (past) threats, and on possible (future) threats, with the description of potential direct and indirect consequences, and the assessment of frequency (likelihood), impact strengths, and their relevance to the ReNEW Living Labs (LL).

Building blocks and correlating data sources that can be useful for the LL will be provided. These building blocks shall serve as baseline supporting: the planning, operation and evaluation and the impacts assessment of the solutions developed in the ReNEW project. Building blocks can comprise catalogues, checklists, methodologies, models and tools for the project and the requirements for their adaptation to be applied in the ReNEW LLs. These can as well be specifications and analyses. The aim is that these building blocks can be incorporated into ReNEW and enhanced, adapted and configured according to the specific ReNEW functional, geographical or processing requirements. This will also include the identification, analysis, and linkage of data source for the models and simulation tools to be configured for ReNEW and to evaluate the ReNEW LL scenarios and measures.

In the further course of the project, a Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF) will be created to enable the quantification based on the developed model characteristics. This includes the identification and development of KPIs and metrics covering the areas of sustainability and resilience and will also be accompanied by cost-benefit analyses to help establish current baselines for the LL and to validate the comparison with the application of ReNEW concepts, processes, technologies, and other innovations.

A set of strategies on resilience and agility for IWT infrastructures as part of intermodal chains including climate adaptation (medium/long term) and agility (short-term, ad-hoc) measures will be developed. These strategies will subsequently be evaluated as a part of the RSQF to identify/prioritise actions in the Living Labs. What-if scenarios will be developed to evaluate the implementation of climate adaptation measures to increase resilience and sustainability; stress tests will be defined/implemented e.g., concerning extreme weather situations.

2.2 Deliverable Structure and General Methodology

This document is the first of three versions, so some of the mentioned objectives may be addressed at a later stage. This document contains the first version of the threat scenario catalogue (Section 3) which covers the risks and hazards to inland water transportation. Initially, the catalogue was developed based on literature research and surveys of project partners. The ReNEW Living Labs were then asked to provide their assessment considering the relevance, impact strength and likelihood of occurrence for each event.

Although the GA mentions both "threat scenario catalogue" and "hazards and vulnerability scenario catalogue," which essentially mean the same, we have decided to differentiate between the two terms. Initially, we identified threats and hazards (both classified as "events") and requested assessments from the partners in the LL (as previously stated). Using these assessments, we can calculate the probable risks, particularly with regard to the likelihood of occurrence. These risks will also be influenced by the vulnerabilities of the different systems. As the project progresses, we will select the events that are relevant for the LL and conduct a detailed risk assessment based on the likelihood of occurrence and a vulnerability analysis.

Section 4 provides an overview of sustainability and resilience, which are important factors for IWT. Since different stakeholders have different perspectives, an overview of key performance indicators (KPIs) is provided, which can be selected and further investigated based on their relevance to each stakeholder group. In the later stages of the project, KPIs will be selected and further refined to be integrated in the Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework.

The document also provides a general overview of the Cost-Benefit Analysis and the approach to be taken in the ReNEW project (Section 4.4).

It also introduces building blocks and data sources (which will be elaborated in more detail in Section 5. Building blocks and data sources may be relevant for each stakeholder group and can be customized to meet their specific requirements. Building blocks refer to the fundamental components that make up the data, models, simulations, and optimizer spaces in the project. These building blocks will be adapted and concretized based on the requirements of each stakeholder group. To identify relevant building blocks and data sources, the project team will need to scope what already exists within the living labs' stakeholders and what is available in open sources or under license. As there are many tools available, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), simulations, and planning tools, it is necessary to identify what can be reused or developed, either in WP1 or WP3,

depending on data availability. The objective is to create a comprehensive set of building blocks that can be tailored to meet the specific needs of each stakeholder group in the project.

The conclusion and the next steps in the project are described in (Section 6).

2.3 Mapping the ReNEW Output

Table 1 maps the ReNEW Grant Agreement (GA) commitments to the project's specific outputs and effort, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outcomes and work to complete.

Table 1: Adherence to ReNEW's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D1.1 Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v1		
Hazards and Vulnerabilities scenarios catalogue, and Resilience and Sustainability KPIs and Cost Benefit Analysis, Data sources 1st Release		
Task T1.1: Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks		
Provide the building blocks serving as baseline supporting: the planning, operation and evaluation and the impacts assessment of FPM(I) and autonomous barges; the Digital Twins as well as the assessment and benchmarking of Emissions Neutral Solutions as these will be tested in the LL scenarios)		
ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST1.1.1 Hazards and vulnerabilities in IW Transport	Define risks and hazards to IWT as part of intermodal chains. Identify, profile and catalogue factors like extreme climate events, low water, floods, ice, technical and human failures, and infrastructural bottlenecks in IWT, connected to long distance and urban scenarios per the Living Labs requirements. Consider also covering physical and cyberthreats similarly to technical and human failures, and their consequences and impacts to the IWT system. Create a threat scenarios catalogue based on known (past) threats, and on possible (future) threats with analysis (ranking) of cascading effects, frequency and impact strengths, and their relevance to the LLs.	Section 3 outlines the Hazards and Vulnerabilities scenarios catalogue. Section 3.2. is divided into five subsections, according to different threat categories/events: Labour oriented/Pandemic, natural phenomenon events, disruption events, crime, and cyber-attacks, operational disruption events, and other disruption events. The catalogue was created based on the past and future threats, including also the description of potential direct and indirect consequences related to identified threats, hazards, risks and vulnerabilities. All the aforementioned events are assessed by the ReNEW living labs.

<p>ST1.1.2 Models and tools and related data sources for IW Hazards and Vulnerabilities</p>	<p>Describe Models and IT tools for networks, traffic and bottlenecks, emissions etc. Network models will include IWT and multimodal routing, infrastructures as seaports and terminals and inland ports. Models will be capturing the operational characteristics of IWT network and infrastructures, including environmental aspects as seasonality in draught and river flows.</p> <p>To support mitigation scenarios, transshipment and interoperability with rail and road transport will be covered, identifying terminals and relevant infrastructures, and further refined in ST1.2 through semantic models and Knowledge Graph. ReNEW will reuse and extend IW-NET developed models for strategies such as collaborative port and locks solutions for e.g., low water scenarios and corridor management. Environmental and life-cycle aspects will also be considered for terminal infrastructures and vessel models (ship engines, stern and bow rudders), including emission (CO₂, SO_x, NO_x, PM) models based on fuel consumption in moving/hotel mode, tide/current, sailing restrictions, routing on IWT, fairway water depth and flow rate, upstream/downstream including currents and tides calculations.</p> <p>Tools will fully support Web-GIS visualisation. Simulation tools will allow tests of new technologies, resilience, and agility strategies. Additionally, hydrological models and tools will assist in the assessment concerning navigability on waterways. Identify, analyse, and link data sources for the models and the simulation tools and the evaluation of the ReNEW LL scenarios and measures, including transport networks and infrastructures (capacities and costs), commodities and cargo flows (origin/destination matrices, amounts per commodity), routes. Access and link TEN-T network data, and inland ENC data for European countries according to the European inland ECDIS standard (CESNIEU Standards Committee for the Inland Navigation Domain), and traffic data on locks and waterway segments</p>	<p>As this deliverable is a first of the three versions, the first release of models (e.g., Ontology for Simulation, Cost-Benefit-Analysis Model) and data sources (e.g., River Information Services) are identified in the Sections 5.1 and 5.2.</p>
ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
<p>ST1.1.3 Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF), KPIs and metrics</p>	<p>Develop joint/correlated resilience and sustainability indicators to enable their quantification based on the developed model characteristics. Deliver a Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF) which facilitates quantification of system resilience coupled with a multi-objective optimisation approach, constrained by the necessary condition of positive correlation between measures to enhance resilience and sustainability characteristics, to aid appropriate and optimal decision making in the IWT context.</p> <p>The RSQF considers the dynamic nature of the problem, and in this regard a dynamic equilibrium restricted assignment model is proposed to simulate system(s) performance evolution. The temporal dimension (i.e.</p>	<p>The Section 4.3 contains general overview of resilience and sustainability KPIs, metrics and measures which could be important for the ReNEW Living Labs.</p> <p>In Section 4.4 an overview about Cost Benefit Analysis and the potential procedure to be applied in ReNEW is described.</p> <p>A Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework will be created in the further course of the</p>

	<p>short and longer term impacts), associated with the progressive response of the system(s) to a time-varying impact requires that the analysis formulation of the system(s) response and the assessment of its corresponding resilience require such a dynamic approach which takes into consideration aspects of the perturbation, as well as the system impedance, i.e. resistance to alter its previous state due to the actual capacity of adaptation to the changes and the state of knowledge of the current situation, the system(s) dependency/interdependency, capacity building systems, and the evolving stress level.</p> <p>Moreover, the uncertainty involved in the system hyper-parameters, e.g., system(s) redundancy, impedance, adaptability, and vulnerability, are incorporated in the RSQF. Develop a set of resilience and sustainability measures, KPIs, and metrics accounting for economic, ecological, and socio-economic factors to support cost-benefit analysis to help establishing current baselines for the LLs and will let comparison with the application of the ReNEW concepts, processes, technologies, and other innovations.</p>	<p>project (i.e., in the further versions of the deliverable).</p>
<p>ST1.1.4 Resilience and Agility strategies</p>	<p>Develop a set of strategies on resilience and agility for IWT infrastructures as part of intermodal chains including climate adaptation (medium/long term) and agility (short-term, ad-hoc) measures. These strategies will subsequently be evaluated as a part of the RSQF to identify/prioritise actions in the Living Labs. What-if scenarios will be developed to evaluate the implementation of climate adaptation measures to increase resilience and sustainability; stress tests will be defined/implemented e.g., concerning extreme weather situations.</p> <p>For the selection of the most relevant for ReNEW strategies a serious gaming approach will also be introduced supported by a (real time) resilience dashboard (adapted from the one developed in the H2020 PRECINCT project). Based on specific climate change related scenarios, cooperative resilience strategies will be developed during role-play games, considering different options of shifting routes, modes, schedules, and specific uses of vessel enabled solutions including Autonomy and modular Platforms (WP2).</p>	<p>The first release of strategies will be included in the second version of the deliverable, according to the Grant Agreement.</p>

3 Hazards and Vulnerabilities Scenario Catalogue

The purpose of this deliverable is to create a so-called scenario catalogue, which will contain identified events, and related risks, hazards, threats and vulnerabilities in IWT. The identified « events » will serve as a baseline for the selection of use cases necessary for the different Living Labs. In a first step all events collected will be assessed by the partners responsible for the LL taking into account the general relevance, the impact strength as well as the likelihood of occurrence.

3.1 Definitions

In order to get a better understanding and clear distinction, it is necessary to explain the terms that can be found in the catalogue as well as in the Grant Agreement of the ReNEW project.

Threat:

Threats can be defined as malicious, deliberate physical or electronic attacks, the execution of which is generally intentional [1], [2]. The U.S. Department of Homeland Security defines a threat as "a natural or man-made event, person, facility, or action that has or implies the potential to harm life, information, operations, the environment, and/or property." [3].

A threat is typically an external source of risk to an organization and is mainly caused by people. In addition, an internal source of risk, such as an insider threat, can occasionally also be represented by a threat. Insider threat is defined by the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) that an insider will use his authorized access to harm the department's mission, resources, people, facilities, information, equipment, networks, or systems. This could happen intentionally or accidentally. Insider threats can take many different forms, including physical harm, espionage, sabotage, theft, and cybercrime.

Hazard:

A hazard is a natural or man-made potential unintentional damage. Natural occurrences are storms, floods, etc., and might include disruptions of supplies such as power, gas, or water. Moreover, an accidental chemical spill might also happen [1], [2].

Hazards include (according to the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction [4] and as mentioned in the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 [5], and listed in alphabetical order) biological, environmental, geological, hydrometeorological and technological processes and occurrences.

- Environmental hazards: these hazards may have biological, ecological, and chemical risks. These may be brought about by physical or chemical contamination of the air, water, and soil, as well as environmental degradation.

- Geological or geophysical hazards are caused by processes occurring inside the earth. Examples include earthquakes, volcanic activity and emissions, and related geophysical events such as surface collapses, mass movements, landslides, and rockslides.
- Hazards associated with hydrometeorology might be atmospheric, hydrological, or oceanic. Examples include coastal storm surges, drought, heatwaves, tropical cyclones (sometimes referred to as typhoons and hurricanes), floods, especially flash floods, and hurricanes. Other risks like landslides, wildland fires, locust plagues, epidemics, and the movement and dispersion of poisonous compounds and volcanic eruption material may also be affected by hydrometeorological conditions.
- Technological hazards result from unfavourable business or technological situations, risky procedures, faulty infrastructure, or certain human activities. Examples include chemical spills, toxic waste, dam failures, transport accidents, manufacturing explosions, and radioactive and hazardous waste.

Some of the environmental and geological/geophysical hazards have significant contributions from hydrometeorological elements. Tsunamis are hard to classify because, despite being caused by undersea earthquakes and other geological occurrences, they essentially become an oceanic process that manifests as a hazard associated with coastal water.

The effects of a natural hazard occurrence may potentially immediately result in technological hazards.

Vulnerability:

Vulnerability can be defined as an operational attribute or physical feature which sets an organization susceptible to a particular threat or hazard. Unlike both above terms (threats and hazards), the vulnerability is the only area that can be modified and influenced [1].

The United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction [6] describes vulnerability as the circumstances resulting from physical, social, economic, and environmental elements or processes that make a person, a community, assets, or systems more vulnerable to the effects of hazards.

Concerning cyber security, computer security vulnerabilities can be classified further [7]. This is done by including various criteria, such as where the vulnerability exists, what caused it, and how it could be exploited.

These are some broader categories of vulnerability types relevant to cyber/computer security:

- Vulnerabilities in the network, i.e., problems with a network's hardware or software that expose it to outside intrusion. Insecure Wi-Fi access points and poorly configured firewalls are two examples.
- Vulnerabilities in the operating system can be explained as flaws in an operating system that hackers can exploit to gain access to or damage an asset. Default accounts, which may exist in some OS installations, and hidden backdoor programs are two examples.

- Human Vulnerabilities, the human element is the weakest link in many cybersecurity architectures. User errors have the potential to expose sensitive data, create exploitable access points for attackers, and disrupt systems [7].
- Vulnerabilities in the process. Specific process controls can introduce vulnerabilities (or a lack thereof). One example is the use of insecure passwords (which may also fall under human vulnerabilities) [7].

Likelihood:

According to ISO 31000:2018(en) Risk management – Guidelines [8], the term **likelihood** determines the chance something happens. This term is independent of any definition or measurement; also independent from being determined objectively or subjectively, qualitatively or quantitatively. The description might be in general terms or in a mathematical way (e.g., frequency or probability [extent to which something is likely to occur]).

Some languages miss a direct translation of the term ‘likelihood’. In these cases, the term ‘probability’ is used mostly. The issue here is that the term ‘probability’ is often used in a very narrow mathematical interpretation. This might lead to misunderstandings.

In the context of ReNEW, a differentiation between likelihood and frequency will be made. The likelihood will be assessed using the criteria certain, likely, probable, unlikely, and rare.

Frequency:

According to the US Department of Homeland Security [3] frequency is defined as the number of occurrences in a defined period.

The concepts of **likelihood and frequency** are not synonymous, but both bring almost the same information in the risk assessment. Frequency is the number of occurrences in a time window of time. The likelihood is the probability of occurrence of an impact that affects the studied ecosystem. Choosing between frequency and likelihood depends on the available data source.

Against the background of ReNEW frequency will be used within the context of the Cost Benefit Analysis to estimate the probability of occurrence in the future (see Section 4.4).

Frequency can be measured by taking a specific period in the past, e.g., 1 year or 5 years, or 10 years, and examining how often the event occurred during that period. When taking past years into the calculation, the number of occurrences that happened might show the number of future occurrences within the same period taking an unchanged setting into account.

Consequences:

Based on ISO 31000:2018(en) Risk management – Guidelines [8], consequences might be certain or uncertain and may be positive or negative. The declaration of consequences can be in a quantitative or qualitative way. Consequences also might grow exponentially taking cascading and cumulative effects into account.

The US Department of Homeland Security [3] already divides the definition of the term “Consequences” into direct and indirect consequences:

Direct consequences:

An immediate result of an event, incident, or occurrence.

Example: The hurricane's direct consequences included loss of life and property damage.

- Injuries, loss of life, on-site business interruption, immediate remediation costs, and damage to property and infrastructure, as well as the environment, can be direct consequences.
- The difference between direct and indirect consequences can sometimes be unclear, but what is of relevance regarding risk analysis is
 - a) To capture the likely effects - whether they are designated as direct or indirect
 - b) To define what is included in direct consequences and what is included in indirect consequences, and
 - c) to be consistent throughout the entire analysis.

Within the direct consequences, the economic consequences are also highlighted. Economic consequences are described as the impact of a single incident, event, or occurrence on the value of the property or the production, trade, distribution, or use of income, wealth, or commodities.

Example: The hurricane's economic impact was the loss of the company's trucking fleet. In the context of homeland security risk, economic consequences are typically assessed as negative and measured in monetary units.

Indirect consequences [3]:

The impact is caused by a direct consequence, subsequent cascading effects, and/or related decisions rather than a direct consequence of an event, incident, or occurrence.

Example: Reduced commerce and tourism were among the hurricane's indirect consequences in the months that followed.

- Indirect consequences can be the implementation of new laws, policies, risk mitigation strategies, or investments, contagion health effects, supply-chain economic consequences, property value reductions, stock market effects, and long-term cleanup efforts.
- It is critical to account for indirect consequences in risk assessments because they may have greater and longer-lasting effects than direct consequences.
- Indirect effects are also known as ripple, multiplier, general equilibrium, macroeconomic, secondary, and tertiary effects.

Risk:

Based on the US Department of Homeland Security [3], the risk is described as the possibility of an unfavourable outcome as a result of an incident, event, or occurrence, as determined by its likelihood and associated consequences. On a more detailed level, the calculation of risk can be done with the inclusion of vulnerability assessments.

According to ISO 31000:2018(en) Risk management – Guidelines [8] risk is defined as the impact of uncertainty on objectives.

A risk can be seen as an 'irregularity' meaning deviation from the expected. This deviation might be in a positive or negative way or both towards aims or objectives. A risk can relate to, create or even result in threats and opportunities. A concrete risk is defined by the individual risk source, the potential events, discovered consequences, and determined likelihood.

3.2 Scenario Catalogue – Version 1

The identified events and related threats and hazards, including additional information, are listed below. They are divided into different categories and corresponding subchapters. Each category is preceded by a table containing a short description of the events, the short description is linked, and the links lead to the detailed description of the corresponding event. The LL were asked to give their assessment of each event in terms of relevance, impact strength, and likelihood. This is also shown in the tables below allocated to each event category (Table 2, Table 3, Table 4, Table 5, Table 6, Table 7).

As already mentioned in the introduction section the following LL are planned for the ReNEW project and the partners responsible have assessed the events.

- Living Lab #1 – Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchromodality City Logistics Hub
- Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway management – DIW2024
- Living Lab #3 - Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, in addition, to boosting modal shift
- Living Lab #4 –Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

The Living Labs have assessed the events using the online whiteboard Miro, according to the following criteria (Figure 1 and Figure 2)

Relevance and impact strength :

- high
- medium
- low
- none

Assessment of the likelihood of occurrence :

- E-Certain
- D-Likely
- C-Probable
- B-Unlikely
- A-Rare

Figure 1: Extract from Miro whiteboard, tools for assessment

Figure 2: Example for the assessment of an event

The events listed below can lead both directly and indirectly to other disruptions, for example, natural phenomenon disruption events can lead to operational disruptions, just as the operational disruptions can stand for themselves or be a consequence of each other.

3.2.1 Labour-oriented / Pandemic

The efficient functioning of IWT depends highly on labour necessary for operating, and maintaining vessels, infrastructures, etc. The working circumstances of IWT employees could be difficult. For example, according to the study « Living and working conditions in inland navigation in Europe » [9], « the fact that vessels cross borders daily in the most major rivers in the various regions means that the crews of these vessels are subject to different countries’ laws and regulations all the time and that they sometimes even fall through the gaps in the laws and regulations, which must have a serious impact on their living and working conditions ». The importance of guaranteeing good working conditions, regular education, and decent salaries [10] in inland waterway transport is very important to prevent a shortage of employees, work-related injuries, human failures, and possible strikes, which ultimately results in uninterrupted business processes. Table 2 shows the threats related to labour and pandemic.

Table 2: Overview of labour-oriented/pandemic disruption events

Event		Assessment			
		LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4
<u>Work-related injury</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	Low None A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Low Low A-Rare	Low Low B-Unlikely
<u>Shortage of labour</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	Medium High C-Probable	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Low Medium E- Certain	Medium Medium C-Probable
<u>Shortage of skills</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High High C-Probable	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Low High E- Certain	Medium Medium C-Probable
<u>Workers' strikes</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	Medium Medium B-Unlikely	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None Low A-Rare	Low Low B-Unlikely
<u>Human Failures</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High High D-Likely	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Medium High C-Probable	Medium Medium A-Rare
<u>Lockdown</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	None None C-Probable	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Low Low B-Unlikely	Low Low A-Rare

Work-related injury

Hazard

Description

Personal/occupational accident

Vulnerabilities

- Poor security and safety measures
- Untrained staff
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of infrastructure, barge, and equipment maintenance

Direct consequences

- Personal hardships (pain and suffering)
- Loss of income/increased costs; In case of injury, IWT operations may face direct costs as well (canceling a trip to provide medical assistance or having the need to hire/rent additional staff)

Indirect consequences

- Increased unnecessary costs such as medical expenses, compensation or insurance
- Reduced productivity
- Poor company reputation
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Possible litigation

Shortage of labour

Hazard

Description

Crew, lock personnel and traffic coordination; e.g., due to high sick leave

Vulnerabilities

- Insufficient staff
- Age pyramid of the crews (aging workforce)
- Unattractive job/working conditions

Direct consequences

- Unscheduled lock or bridge outage/closures
- Difficulty in recruiting and training replacement crew members as older crew members retire

Indirect consequences

- Increased congestion
- Barge accidents
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Loss of business
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Decreasing the reputation of the transport mode/company
- Degradation of inland waterway transport
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods

Shortage of skills

Hazard

Description

Developing new devices for data processing and validating the collected data is labour intensive and requires a high degree of technological knowledge in analytics, statistics and software modelling [11], as well as experts such as computer scientists, mathematicians and data scientists.

Vulnerabilities

- Difficulty in planning for uncertain future
- Rapid changes in digitalization
- Lack of training

Direct consequences

- Failure to uptake new technologies/waste of resources as operation goes back to status quo
- Loss of cargo or cargo damage (e.g., container falls into the water because of the lack of knowledge of proper cargo handling)
- Infrastructure and equipment damage
- Loss of life
- Stop operation in ports

Indirect consequences

- Increased congestion
- Barge accidents
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Loss of business
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Decreasing the reputation of the transport mode/company
- Degradation of inland waterway transport
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods

Workers' strikes

Threat

Description

Employees' collective refusal to work under the conditions demanded by their employers [12]. Strikes occur for a variety of reasons, the most common of which are economic conditions (defined as an economic strike and intended to improve wages and benefits) or labour practices (intended to improve work conditions). Other strikes may occur as a result of solidarity with other striking unions or from jurisdictional disputes between two unions. Strikes can also be called solely for political reasons.

Vulnerabilities

- Low, delayed or no salary (payment)
- Poor working conditions
- Lack of safety and security
- Corruption
- Political instability

Direct consequences

- Loss of income (striking workers)
- Reduced safety
- Stop operation in ports (Ports)

Indirect consequences

- Failure or delay in the transport of goods
- Decreasing the reputation of the transport mode/company
- Reduced productivity
- Degradation of inland waterway transport
- Loss of investments
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Shortage of labour force availability due to the negative image created by strikes

Human Failures

Hazard

Description

A human failure is an unintentional action or decision. Some failures are slips or lapses, which are frequently "actions that were not as planned" or unintended actions. Other types of failures include mistakes or errors in judgment or decision-making in which the "intended actions are incorrect," i.e., when one does the wrong actions having faith that this is correct. These typically occur when a person does not know the proper way to carry out a task, either because it is new and unprecedented, or because they have not been prepared (or both) [13].

Vulnerabilities

- Poor training
- Poor working conditions
- Stress and fatigue
- Limited communication
- Poor employee security and safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Shipping accidents
- Injury to crew members and other workers
- Unscheduled lock or bridge outage/closures
- Loss of cargo and other valuable assets (e.g., container falls into the water)
- Property damage
- Loss of life
- Stop operation in ports

Indirect consequences

- Increased congestion
- Barge accidents
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Loss of business
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Decreasing the reputation of the transport mode/company
- Degradation of inland waterway transport
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods

Lockdown

Hazard

Description

The decision of the authorities. A lockdown can be defined as an emergency in which people are not permitted to enter, leave, or move freely in a building or area due to danger, or as a period in which people are not permitted to leave their homes or travel freely due to a dangerous disease [14].

Vulnerabilities

- Failure to meet safety criteria (audits)
- Redundancy of workers
- Difficulty in obtaining maintenance and repairs

Direct consequences

- Unplanned downtime according to regulations
- Demand uncertainty
- Loss of income
- Reduced safety

Indirect consequences

- Long-term strategic planning is unrealistic
- The bankruptcy of the transport company;
- Unemployment
- Loss of business
- Imbalances in: hardware (vessels/transport units/equipment) and flows of goods
- Inaccessibility of other countries, even in the single market

3.2.2 Natural Phenomenon Disruption Events

Natural disruption events can have a significant impact on inland waterway transport. These events may be various such as storms/tornados, hailstorms, high and low waters, and cold or ice. The resulting disruptions can cause direct and indirect consequences such as property/vessel damage, loss of life or injury, increased congestion, and barge accidents. For example, according to Schweighofer, J., [15] long periods of drought may lead to reduced discharge and low water levels, resulting in limited cargo-carrying vessel capacity and increased transportation costs. Vinke, F. et al. [16] claim that water level changes may strongly affect the fleet composition, occupancy, and arrivals at the origin or destination.

As already mentioned, IWT plays an important role in global trade, especially when the emphasis is on sustainability, and by understanding the impact of natural disruptions, it is possible to achieve a resilient and sustainable IWT. In this respect, below are listed possible natural phenomenon disruption events, which are assessed by the ReNEW project Living Labs. In Table 3, threats related to natural phenomenon disruption events are listed.

Table 3: Overview of natural phenomenon disruption events

Event		Assessment			
		LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4
<u>Storm/Tornado (Strong wind)</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Medium	High	Low	Low
<u>Hailstorm</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Low • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Medium	High	Low	Low
<u>Thunderstorm</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Low • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Medium	High	Low	None
<u>Sandstorm</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Low • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	Medium	None	Low	None
<u>Flood / Tsunami / Storm surge</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: B-Unlikely 	Medium	High	Medium	High
<u>High waters</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	Medium	High	High	High
<u>Heavy rain</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Medium	High	Medium	Low
<u>Drought</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: C-Probable 	Medium	High	Low	Low

<u>Low waters</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	High High A-Rare	High High C-Probable	High High E- Certain	High High D-Likely
<u>Heat</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Low • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Medium Low D-Likely	High High D-Likely	None None D-Likely	Low Low D-Likely
<u>Dry warm periods</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: B-Unlikely 	High High B-Unlikely	High Medium D-Likely	Low Low D-Likely	Low Low D-Likely
<u>Cold</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Low • Impact strength: None • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	Low None A-Rare	High Medium B-Unlikely	Low Low B-Unlikely	Low Low D-Likely
<u>Ice</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: C-Probable 	High High C-Probable	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Medium High A-Rare	Medium Medium A-Rare
<u>Snow avalanche</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	High High A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	None None B-Unlikely
<u>Heavy snow / Snowdrift</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	High Medium A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None B-Unlikely	Low Low C-Probable
<u>Fog</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: Low • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	High Low D-Likely	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Medium Medium D-Likely	Low Low E- Certain
<u>Landslide</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	High Medium A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Low Low A-Rare	High High B-Unlikely
<u>Rock avalanche</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	High Medium A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	High High B-Unlikely
<u>Earthquake</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Low • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: B-Unlikely 	Low Medium B-Unlikely	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	Low Low B-Unlikely
<u>Volcano eruption</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	High High A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	Medium Medium B-Unlikely
<u>Orogeny</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	High High A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	High High B-Unlikely
<u>Rift / Sinkhole</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: A-Rare 	High High A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	Low Low B-Unlikely

Storm/Tornado (Strong wind)

Hazard

Description

A small-scale, strongly rotating column of air with a vertical axis of rotation that is in contact with the ground [17], [18]

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance, resulting in unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training, poor employee safety awareness
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions

Direct consequences

- Loss of goods (e.g., container falls into the water)
- Property damage
- Loss of life
- Stop operation in ports (Ports)
- Trees and branches fallen on overhead wiring (Trains)
- Trees and branches fallen on the road (Road)
- Due to a storm on the sea, seawater is swirled up, taken by the wind and the salt covers insulators of the overhead wiring (Train)
- Reconstruction of the infrastructure (costs)

Indirect consequences

- The bankruptcy of the transport company
- Unemployment
- Slow recovery of traffic
- Increased congestion
- Barge accidents
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Loss of business
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods

Hailstorm

Hazard

Description

Sudden and heavy fall of hail

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Service outage
- Property/vessel damage
- Loss of life or injury
- Damaged cars (Automobile terminal)
- Reconstruction of the infrastructure (costs)
- Navigation difficulties

Indirect consequences

- Slow recovery of traffic
- Increased congestion
- Barge accidents
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Loss of business, bankruptcy of the transport company, unemployment
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods

Thunderstorm

Hazard

Description

Thunder and lightning

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Loss of life or injury due to lightning
- Property/infrastructure/vessel damage
- Cargo damage
- Failure of communications systems
- Navigation difficulties

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Loss of business
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Sandstorm

Hazard

Description

Strong winds carry vast amounts of dust and/or sand

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness
- Reduced visibility

Direct consequences

- Road blocked due to sandstorm (Road)
- Damage to barge, infrastructure and equipment
- Cargo damage
- Injury to crew members and other workers
- Stop operation in ports
- Navigation difficulties

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Flood / Tsunami / Storm surge

Hazard

Description

Water stands in urban and rural areas for different reasons

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Closure of roads and bridges
- Landslide risks
- Barge, infrastructure, and equipment damage
- Cargo loss or damage
- Reconstruction of the infrastructure (costs)
- Reduced or limited navigability
- Reduced speed

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Economic activities may come to a standstill

High waters

Hazard

Description

For a significant time, water level is too high for vessels to navigate [19]

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability [20]
- Washed up debris e.g. wood
- Missing bridge clearance
- Submerged traffic signs or obstacles
- Currents
- Reconstruction of the infrastructure (costs)

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Heavy rain

Hazard

Description

Vast amounts of precipitation, possibly in a short time

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Water damage to goods
- Flooding
- Flooded streets (Roads)
- Overloaded sewer system (Road, company premises)
- Damage to river engineering structures occurs during floods (e.g., loose rip rap, ballast layer, pavement, etc.)
- Reconstruction of the infrastructure (costs)
- Navigation difficulties

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Drought

Hazard

Description

A significantly long period with an unusually low amount of precipitation

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Shortage of water which causes navigation difficulties
- A sediment deficit and erosion of riverbeds caused by upstream hydropower plants or silos. A continued erosion may reduce the payload of vessels. A bridges, ports and hydraulic structures might be negatively influenced too.

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Higher congestion because of high temperatures
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Low waters

Hazard

Description

For a significant period of time, the water level is too low for vessels to navigate

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability
- Missing under keel clearance (UKC)
- Reduced speed
- Damage to barges and infrastructures

Remark: "low water" mostly leads to an opportunity to earn more money for the operators.

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Heat

Hazard

Description

Unusual high temperatures for a significant period of time

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Hard-working conditions (All)
- Especially hard-working conditions for shunters (Trains)
- Cabins of straddle carriers/gantry cranes can be unbearably hot (ports)
- Weakening of asphalt (Road, port premises, etc.)
- Track distortions (Train)
- Blow-ups (Road)
- Limited cooling of warehouses (Warehousing)
- Reconstruction of the infrastructure (costs)
- Increased fire risk

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Dry warm periods

Hazard

Description

The correlation between low waters and dry/warm periods

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability
- Missing under keel clearance (UKC)
- Reduced speed
- Damage to barges and infrastructures

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Cold

Hazard

Description

Unusual low temperatures for a significant period of time

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or limited navigability
- Reduced speed
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage
- Freezing locks

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Ice

Hazard

Description

For a significant period of time ice blocks waterways, rail tracks and/or roads or yards.

Vulnerabilities

- Bridges (aqueducts) must be designed for the outward thrust of ice forming in the channel
- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability for non-icebreaking vessels
- Reduced speed
- Damage to barges and infrastructures
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage
- Freezing locks
- Injury of crew members

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Snow avalanche

Hazard

Description

Fast downward moving large amounts of snow

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability for non-icebreaking vessels
- Reduced speed
- Damage to barges and infrastructures
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage
- Injury of crew members

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Heavy Snow / Snowdrift

Hazard

Description

A large heap of snow made by strong wind

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Closed traffic routes for an unforeseeable time
- Frozen locks and equipment
- Navigation difficulties

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced operational capability
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Fog

Hazard

Description

Very small drops of water, forming a thick cloud that reduces visibility [21], and limit operation and navigability.

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of technology to predict or detect fog
- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced visibility (difficulties in navigation and detecting navigational aids)
- Reduced speed
- Increased congestion
- Difficult to detect and avoid other barges, leading to collisions and groundings
- Damage to barges and infrastructures
- Cargo damage

Indirect consequences

- Disruption of the supply chain: The delays and congestion caused by fog can disrupt the supply chain, causing delays in the delivery of goods and affecting the operations of businesses that rely on the waterways for transportation.

Landslide

Hazard

Description

Fast downward moving large amounts of mud/soil and/or debris

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability
- Damage to barges and infrastructures
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Rock avalanche

Hazard

Description

Fast downward moving large amounts of rocks

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability
- Damage to barges and infrastructures
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Earthquake

Hazard

Description

A sudden violent movement of the earth's surface, sometimes causing great damage [22]

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Barges could have been flipped over by the quake, and suffer damages
- The berth can sustain deformation and lateral displacement
- Quay walls can suffer damage [23]
- Reduced or restricted navigability [23]
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Volcano eruption

Hazard

Description

Fluid materials and gasses erupt suddenly from a volcano

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability
- Damage to barges and infrastructures
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Orogeny

Hazard

Description

Orogeny (or orogenesis) is derived from the Greek words oros (mountain) and genesis (origin or mode of formation). The term mountain building indicates that the rate of surface uplift is above the rate of erosion, resulting in the evolution of a lowland area into a mountain system over time. Orogeny is the term used to describe the deformation caused by tectonic plate convergence during mountain formation [24]. In principle, mountain building affects waterways by altering the topography of the landscape, thereby affecting the course of rivers and streams, or by promoting the formation of lakes and wetlands by altering the natural flow of water and impounding water in certain areas. However, the formation of mountains is a process that can span time periods ranging from decades to millions of years. There are also cases where mountains can form more quickly, such as volcanoes or tectonic events that can trigger earthquakes and thus can have a direct impact on waterways [25], [26].

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability
- Damage to barges and infrastructures
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Rift / Sinkhole

Hazard

Description

Sudden appearance of holes or fissures due to weak subsoil

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and infrastructure maintenance
- Unsafe barge, equipment, infrastructure
- Lack of training
- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Lack of safety procedures
- Poor working conditions
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability
- Damage to barges and infrastructures
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- The difficulty for the crew to work safely
- Cargo damage

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

3.2.3 Crime and Cyber Attacks

Inland waterway transport is vulnerable to crime and cyber-attacks. Criminal activities can result in financial losses, damage to infrastructure, etc., while cyber-attacks can compromise e.g. the security of sensitive data [27]. Ensuring the security of IWT is vital for maintaining the smooth flow of goods and people. For example, each digitalised solution should be subject to a certain cyber risk assessment, in order to identify possible cyber threats and risks. In this way, it is possible to monitor them and define appropriate mitigation measures [28]. In Table 4, threats related to crime and cyber-attacks are listed.

Table 4: Overview of crime and cyber attacks

Event		Assessment			
		LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4
Cargo theft	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	Medium Low C-Probable	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None C-Probable	High High B-Unlikely
Data theft	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High Medium C-Probable	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Medium Medium B-Unlikely	High High C-Probable
Blackmail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	None None A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Low Low B-Unlikely	Medium Medium A-Rare
Kidnap/hostage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	None None A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None High A-Rare	None None B-Unlikely
Sabotage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High Medium B-Unlikely	Not relevant for LL2 scope	High Medium B-Unlikely	High High A-Rare
Corruption and insider crime	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High Medium A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Medium Low C-Probable	High High A-Rare
Outbreak of war	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High High B-Unlikely	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	High High C-Probable
Killing spree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	None Medium A-Rare	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	Medium Medium C-Probable
Hybrid attacks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High High C-Probable	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Medium Medium A-Rare	High High E- Certain
Terrorism and terrorist attacks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High High B-Unlikely	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None None A-Rare	Medium Medium E- Certain

Cargo theft

Threat

Description

Cargo theft is among the most concerning threats which affect global supply chains in terms of injuries, economic loss, environmental damage, etc. [29]

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of physical barriers, surveillance, etc.
- Unsecured systems
- Poor employee security awareness

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- Loss of cargo and other valuable assets

Indirect consequences

- “When a single cargo theft accident occurs, the involved supply chain costs six times the cargo value because the accident affects the costs of product replacement, accident handling, increased insurance premium, loss of sales, and negative impact on the business reputation” [29]
- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs
- Delays

Data theft

Threat

Description

Data such as financial information, property, competition information, legal information, and IT security data (user names and passwords, encryption keys, network structure) [30]

Vulnerabilities

- Unsecured systems
- Poor employee security awareness
- Lack of training
- Lack of security measures
- Lack of data security/data redundancy

Remark: This threat usually manifests as a "Denial of Service" (DOS) which half falls under "blackmail" below

Direct consequences

- Theft of sensitive information
- Stop of operations in ports
- Potential accident if data related dangerous goods are manipulated or made unavailable

Indirect consequences

- Potential financial loss for the port that loses information about operations, which prevents it from invoicing the performed operations [31]
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Decreasing the reputation of the transport mode/company
- Potential accident if data related dangerous goods are manipulated or made unavailable

Blackmail

Threat

Description

This threat determines spoken or written information about the intent to punish or injure another person or to inflict an economical loss to an organisation.

Vulnerabilities

- Unsecured systems
- Poor employee security awareness
- Lack of training
- Lack of security measures

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Physical security breach (control system out of order)

Indirect consequences

- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Exposure of client's data
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs

Kidnap/hostage

Threat

Description

Kidnapping refers to confinement without legal authority, whereas hostage refers to a person or entity held as security by a captor [32].

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of physical barriers, surveillance, etc.
- Unsecured systems
- Poor (employee) security awareness

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Physical security breach (control system out of order)
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- Loss of cargo and other valuable assets

Indirect consequences

- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Exposure of client's data
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs

Sabotage

Threat]

Description

Unauthorized individuals can wilfully insert, delete or update information in order to reach economic advantages [33]

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of physical barriers, surveillance, etc.
- Unsecured systems
- Poor employee security awareness

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Damage to barges and infrastructure

Indirect consequences

- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Exposure of client's data
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs
- Delays

Corruption and insider crime

Threat

Description

Passing on information to obtain access to terminal or goods or passive role in case of unlawful entry or pick-up/drop-off

Vulnerabilities

- Poor employee security awareness
- Inadequate laws and regulations

Direct consequences

- Financial losses
- Reduced efficiency and reliability
- Reduced safety and security of cargo and barges

Indirect consequences

- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Exposure of client's data
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs
- Delays

Outbreak of war

Threat

Description

The outbreak of a war may have a strong influence on IWT, disrupting supply chains, damaging infrastructure, etc.

Vulnerabilities

- Difficulty in securing the safety of navigation
- Difficulty in protecting equipment, ports, and barges

Direct consequences

- Loss of goods (e.g., container falls into the water)
- Property damage
- Loss of life and injury
- Stop operation in ports

Indirect consequences

- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion at locks and ports
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction
- Trees and branches fallen on overhead wiring (Trains)
- Trees and branches fallen on road (Road)"

Killing spree

Threat

Description

A sudden and violent attack by an individual or group of individuals, which results in multiple deaths. In the IWT, a killing spree can have large negative consequences, including loss of life, disruption of supply chains, etc.

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of physical barriers, surveillance, etc.
- Unsecured systems
- Poor employee security awareness

Direct consequences

- Loss of human life and injury
- The waterway can be closed or restricted, preventing barges from moving
- Damage to barges and cargo

Indirect consequences

- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs
- Delays

Hybrid attacks

Threat

Description

Hybrid attacks are types of cyberattacks in which the perpetrator combines two or more types of tools to execute the attack [34].

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of physical barriers, surveillance, etc.
- Unsecured systems
- Poor employee security awareness
- Lack of safety and security measures

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Physical security breach (control system out of order)
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- Loss of cargo and other valuable assets

Indirect consequences

- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Exposure of client's data
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs

Terrorism and terrorist attacks

Threat

Description

Terrorism/terrorist attacks are the calculated use of violent action to generate an overall climate of fear in a population and thus achieve a specific political goal [35], [36].

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of physical barriers, surveillance, etc.
- Unsecured systems
- Poor employee security awareness

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Physical security breach (control system out of order)
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- Loss of cargo and other valuable assets

Indirect consequences

- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Exposure of client's data
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs

3.2.4 Operational Disruption Events

Operational disruption events can significantly impact IWT and may include energy breakdown, IT breakdown, infrastructural bottlenecks, etc. These disruptions can also lead to negative consequences such as delays, damage to the infrastructure and vessels, increased costs, etc. Table 5 includes the list of possible operational disruption events assessed by the partners responsible for the ReNEW Living Labs.

Table 5: Overview of operational disruption events

Event		Assessment			
		LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4
Energy breakdown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	High	High	Medium	High
IT breakdown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	High	High	Medium	High
Technical breakdown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	High	High	Medium	High
Shortage of supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Low • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Low	Low	None	High
Shortage of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Low • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Low	Low	None	High
Incipient fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Low	Low	None	High
Accident	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Not relevant for LL2 scope	High	High	High
Leakage of hazardous substances	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: B-Unlikely 	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None	Low	Medium
Infrastructural bottlenecks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: C-Probable 	Not relevant for LL2 scope	High	High	Medium
Infrastructural defaults	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: High • Impact strength: High • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Not relevant for LL2 scope	High	High	Medium
Congestion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Not relevant for LL2 scope	Medium	Medium	Medium
Pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: Medium • Impact strength: Medium • Likelihood of occurrence: D-Likely 	Not relevant for LL2 scope	None	None	High

<u>Faulty of instrumentation</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	<p>High Medium B-Unlikely</p>	Not relevant for LL2 scope	<p>Medium Medium C-Probable</p>	<p>Medium Medium B-Unlikely</p>
<u>Restriction to international access by hostile country</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	<p>High Medium B-Unlikely</p>	Not relevant for LL2 scope	<p>High High A-Rare</p>	<p>High High A-Rare</p>
<u>Dependence on other carriers</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	<p>High High C-Probable</p>	Not relevant for LL2 scope	<p>Low Low C-Probable</p>	<p>Medium Medium C-Probable</p>
Faulty or unavailability of AIS (added by LL3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 			<p>High High C-Probable</p>	

Energy breakdown

Hazard

Description

There is practically no company that could operate without a continuous energy supply of various kinds (e.g., Electricity, gas, diesel). Some companies may maintain operation for a limited period due to stored energy supply (e.g., Diesel tanks for vehicles or emergency power supply). But when these supplies run out, these plants also have to pause operation until the required energy is available.

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of cooperation with other carriers/ stakeholders
- Dependence on a single energy source or supplier

Direct consequences

- Insufficient power to operate locks or provide external fuel to shipping
- Reduced or restricted navigability

Indirect consequences

- A lack of electrical energy may result in an IT breakdown thus production stops.
- Companies moving goods using diesel-powered vehicles probably maintain operation for some time, but later on, movement is impossible.
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

IT breakdown

Hazard

Description

Companies these days rely on IT to organise and execute daily tasks. Without this support, some tasks could still be executed, but most functions come to a stop.

Vulnerabilities

- Poorly protected IT, (e.g., no firewalls, no/insufficient security systems)
- Untrained staff
- Insufficient staff
- Difficulty in obtaining maintenance and repairs
- Poor employee security awareness

Direct consequences

- Failure of dependent systems in the network (e.g. traffic control)

Indirect consequences

- No regularly updated information e.g., on traffic conditions
- No communication
- The temporary or long-term collapse of the offers
- Decreasing speed, availability, and responsiveness
- Since most production, processes and administration tasks in a modern company rely deeply on IT services. If this is unavailable, production might stop, energy supply might be unavailable, and movement of goods could be impossible causing congestion e.g., if truck clearance is unavailable.

Technical breakdown

Hazard

Description

This can be, for example, a technical defect in the production area or a power failure. Producers have to work on raw materials or semi-finished products to add value. Due to a technical breakdown this added value cannot be performed thus orders are delayed (In short: no goods, no transportation)

Vulnerabilities

- Alteration of an area where the service requires an intervention or where the criticality of location might endanger the safety and fluidity of traffic (e.g. breaking lock, the collapse of a crane)
- Missing maintenance of equipment

Direct consequences

- Interruption of production
- Risk of accidents due to defective equipment
- Delay in the transport of goods

Indirect consequences

- Delayed orders at a supplier have effects on subsequent companies: If parts of manufactured objects are missing, the production also in this company stops. This effect is highly visible in the automotive industry using a just-in-time manufacturing model
- Increasing delivery time
- Increasing congestion (e.g., the offshore power supply does not work)
- Increasing costs when transport is shifted to e.g., street

Shortage of supply

Hazard

Description

Disruption in the supply chain, supply problems with materials. Companies highly rely these days on a continuous supply of raw materials or semi-finished products in order to maintain production. Stock-keeping has declined last decades due to economic reasons. If the continuous supply of needed materials is not given, production will be suspended. In the long term, the unavailability of necessary materials and raw materials can also lead to problems for transporters, as there is nothing left to transport.

Vulnerabilities

- "just in time" - production-synchronous delivery of materials and production without intermediate storage [37]

Direct consequences

- Interruption of the production chain
- Delay of goods deliveries, long waiting times

Indirect consequences

- Without production, workers have to be paid without producing efforts. Such a stage might lead to bankruptcy.
- Supply bottleneck
- Loss of production

Shortage of resources

Hazard

Description

Companies highly rely these days on working machinery and/or robots in order to maintain production and thus resources to maintain operation, starting from oil for machinery and ending with paper to print orders. Also, spare parts for machines are often not in stock due to economic reasons.

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of redundancy in materials to service/maintain machinery
- Lack of communication and planning
- Just-in-time stock keeping

Direct consequences

- Failure of machines etc.(technical equipment, loading machines)
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods.

Indirect consequences

- The example of missing oil at machines causes higher abrasion at moving parts thus life cycles (time needed between two revisions or exchange of parts) are shortened and spare parts are needed more often.
- A missing paper might lead to the impossibility of processing tasks
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Incipient fire

Hazard

Description

Each fire starts with a small incipient fire, which should be detected and extinguished immediately otherwise the whole company might be endangered due to fire damage

Vulnerabilities

- Flammable objects/areas
- Lack of barge and equipment maintenance
- Lack of training
- Limited communication
- Lack of regulations
- Lack of security measures
- Poor employee safety awareness

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Damage to cargo
- Loss of life and injury
- Navigational difficulties

Indirect consequences

- When firefighters extinguish a fire usually enormous amounts of water or other extinguishing agents (e.g., foam) are used which might cause water or other damages to production plants and administration buildings. Water damage might be seen as similar to flood damage.
- Firefighters require space to perform their duties causing congestion to roads and maybe areas used to move goods in yards.
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Accident

Hazard

Description

An accident in this case relates to a vehicle or machine hitting another one or parts of buildings. Such an accident might cause loss of vehicle or machinery and/or production material.

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and equipment maintenance
- Lack of training
- Limited communication
- Lack of regulations
- Lack of security measures

Direct consequences

- Physical alterations of waterway infrastructure by dredging (affecting riverbed morphology within the fairway)
- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Damage to cargo
- Loss of life and injury
- Navigational difficulties

Indirect consequences

- Subsequent congestion on traffic routes following an accident might occur due to emergency services, loss of energy supply, fire, etc.
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Leakage of hazardous substances

Hazard

Description

The spillage of hazardous substances poses a significant risk to both the environment and human health (possible contamination of water, soil, air etc.) [38]

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and equipment maintenance
- Lack of training
- Lack of communication
- Insufficient staff
- Poor employee security awareness

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- Loss of cargo and other valuable assets

Indirect consequences

- To seal a leak machinery, sealing material, and/or fire brigades might be necessary. Thus, congestion on access routes, blocking of work areas, and evacuation of buildings could be subsequent action. Delivery and collection of material might be impossible, as well as processes due to evacuated employees could be possible.
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Infrastructural bottlenecks

Hazard

Description

Having fast-growing industrial areas require adequate access routes. If governmental services cannot keep up with growing industry or handling areas, access might be limited. This access is not limited to roads. Rivers and canals including locks as well as Railroads and shunting stations might also be affected.

Vulnerabilities

- The limited capacity of locks and other infrastructure
- Inefficient scheduling

Direct consequences

- Delays
- Increased fuel consumption

Indirect consequences

- Infrastructural bottlenecks might be seen as similar to congestion with a slightly different approach: Locks might have daily limited opening hours and fixed revision periods whereas congestion might be caused by unforeseen events.
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion at locks and ports
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Infrastructural defaults

Hazard

Description

The main Infrastructural defaults are damaged roads, road works and congestion, poor communication networks (slow internet), and delays in rail transportation [39].

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of infrastructure maintenance
- No or low infrastructure investments
- Shortage of personnel in certain industries

Direct consequences

- Disrupting the traffic and the navigation
- Delays in goods transportation
- Delays can, in the worst case, mean a temporary halt to production (due to just-in-time production) [39]

Indirect consequences

- Congestion (bottlenecks)
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Congestion

Hazard

Description

Congestion might be twofold: Road congestion means raw materials/semi-finished goods/products cannot be moved to or from the plant in focus.

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of barge and equipment maintenance
- Lack of training
- Limited communication
- Lack of regulations

Direct consequences

- Delays
- Increased fuel consumption
- Increased emissions

Indirect consequences

- Other companies in need of such material might also suspend production until needed material is available, transports already ordered for these products must also be suspended. Consumers have to wait until products are available.
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods
- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Pollution

Hazard

Description

Water pollution, air pollution, soil pollution, sonor pollution, etc.

Vulnerabilities

- Poor employee security awareness
- Lack of training
- Lack of safety and security measures
- Inadequate regulations
- Lack of infrastructure, barge, and equipment maintenance

Direct consequences

- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- Loss of cargo

Indirect consequences

- Habitat deterioration
- Quality of life deterioration
- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs
- Delays

Faulty of instrumentation

Hazard

Description

Instrument breakdown and a lack of spares: unforeseen failure can halt production, resulting in severe consequences. This can as well include incorrect equipment usage, incorrect system failure diagnosis, instrumentation that has been incorrectly specified as well as instrumentation that has been improperly installed [40].

Vulnerabilities

- Obsolete equipment
- Lack of equipment maintenance
- Lack of training (e.g., improper handling of equipment)
- Inadequate security (cyber-attacks)

Direct consequences

- Data leakage
- Accidents and incidents due to failure of control equipment
- Interruption of operations
- Unsafe working conditions
- Damage to barges and infrastructure
- Loss of life or injury to crew members
- Loss of cargo

Indirect consequences

- Broken trust resulting in loss of traffic/clients
- Damage to reputation
- Increased costs
- Delays

Restriction to international access by a hostile country

Threat

Description

Hostile country restricts international access to its waters or disrupts navigation conditions by malicious operation of river infrastructure

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of cooperation with stakeholders/countries
- Lack of alternative routes and transport modes

Direct consequences

- Reduced or restricted navigability
- Delays or disruptions in the transportation of goods

Indirect consequences

- Loss of business
- Increased costs
- Congestion
- Reduced productivity
- Decreased customer satisfaction

Dependence on other carriers

Vulnerabilities

Description

During the transportation of goods, the customer depends on different carriers, e.g., container transportation by ship, onward transportation by truck, or by rail. Any delay affecting a carrier can cause delays among others and the goods will not be delivered on time.

Direct consequences

- Delays in delivery of cargo
- Damage or loss of cargo
- Increased costs

Indirect consequences

- Inability to meet clients' demand
- Limited flexibility

3.2.5 Other Disruption Events

In addition to the aforementioned events, it is possible to single out a few that are related to bureaucracy and economical/regulatory events. In this respect, Table 6 and Table 7 contain listed events assessed by the partners responsible for the ReNEW Living Labs.

Table 6: Overview of other disruption events - Bureaucracy

Event		Assessment			
		LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4
<u>Change of law/regulations</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact Strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High High C-Probable	High High C-Probable	High High D-Likely	High High D-Likely

Table 7: Overview of other disruption events - Economical/Regulatory

Event		Assessment			
		LL1	LL2	LL3	LL4
<u>Protectionism</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact Strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High High A-Rare	Low Low B-Unlikely	Medium High D-Likely	High High D-Likely
<u>Economical condition</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: • Impact Strength: • Likelihood of occurrence: 	High Medium B-Unlikely	Low Low B-Unlikely	Medium Medium C-Probable	High High D-Likely

Change of law/regulations

Hazard

Description

New laws/regulations or modifications can impact processes and/or can lead to higher bureaucracy, e.g. customs regulations, fiscal regulations, and environmental laws [41]

Vulnerabilities

- Lack of knowledge
- Difficulty in adapting to new laws/regulations
- Limited resources to implement new requirements
- Different laws/regulations between countries

Direct consequences

- Changes in the costs
- Changes in equipment processes or types of cargo that can be transported
- Changes in responsibilities

Indirect consequences

- The level of complexity of processes rises due to higher bureaucracy
- Uncertainty about how and when laws/regulations have to be fulfilled
- Increased costs
- Delays

Protectionism

Hazard

Description

Protectionism occurs when countries impose import restrictions on their economies. This can include higher tariffs (a type of import tax) as well as quotas and embargoes. Other types of protectionism, such as domestic subsidies that give industries unfair advantages, can be less obvious [42].

For example, countries refuse to allow innovations in order to protect their obsolete fleet

Vulnerabilities

- Missing regional integration agreements, such as free trade agreements [43]
- Governmental restrictions [44]

Direct consequences

- An obsolete fleet may require additional maintenance
- No free trade
- A decline in trade [42]
- Higher prices for some goods [42]
- A form of subsidy for protected industries. Some jobs in these industries may be saved, but others will most likely be lost [42]
- High costs for external parties
- The benefits of previous trade liberalization would be lost [43]
- Global real incomes would fall, and there would be a risk that the supply of goods and services would be reduced [43].

Indirect consequences

- Damage to the environment (higher emissions)
- Decreasing the reputation of the transport mode/company
- A limited supply of goods and services in the long term

Economical condition

Hazard

Description

Economic conditions are the current state of affairs in a country's or geographical region's overall economy. The conditions change over time as a result of various business and economic cycles [45].

Vulnerabilities

- Stagnation of the economic activity
- Unbalanced industrial development [46], [47]
- Low industrialization level [46], [47]
- Poor economic foundation [46], [47]

Direct consequences

- Decrease in profit and return
- Rise in unemployment

Indirect consequences

- Reduction of maintenance (infrastructure)
- Reductions in income and wealth [46], [47]
- Increased uncertainty about future employment and income [46], [47].

4 Achieving Resilience and Sustainability through Proper KPIs and Cost Benefit Analysis

According to the GA, joint/correlated resilience and sustainability indicators shall be developed in order to deliver a Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework which facilitates quantification of system resilience.

As a first step, an extensive literature review was conducted for this purpose and sustainability and resilience KPIs were identified.

Since the 4 LLs envisaged for ReNEW are very different and therefore have different requirements, a general overview of existing sustainability and resilience KPIs was provided. At a later stage of the project selected KPIs relevant to the LL will be further investigated and specified on the basis of the requirements for the corresponding use cases from the LL.

Another component of the RSQF are cost-benefit analyses to help establish current baselines for the LL and to validate the comparison with the application of ReNEW concepts, processes, technologies, and other innovations. At this stage of the project no detailed information about costs and benefits is available. Due to this, this document provides a general overview about cost benefit analyses and describes the procedure to be executed in the course of the project.

4.1 Background/Overview

In the following the terms « resilience » and « sustainability » will be analysed. Furthermore, disruption phases in the resilience and sustainability context will be elaborated. The term « Key Performance Indicators » and its importance are explained and relevant resilience and sustainability KPIs will be described. In the course of the project and based on the results from the LL, the KPIs will be further investigated and categorized according to their importance and continuously updated.

4.2 Sustainability, Resilience and Disruption Phases

Sustainability is the ability to last over time without losing performance and stay respecting standards and regulations. A sustainable business may be defined as the ability of the organization to reduce the negative effects of business activity through the provision of socially inclusive working conditions (social sustainability), strong economic performance (economic sustainability), and eco-friendly transportation services (environmental sustainability) [48]. According to Marchese, D. et al. [49], the diversity of potential business disruptions are less likely to have an impact on supply chains, when economic, social, and environmental aspects of sustainability are equally considered, which may also apply to the IWT sector. For example, organizations (that operate in the IWT sector) with a diverse economic portfolio (economic sustainability) are less susceptible to being affected by regional or industry-specific downturns. Furthermore, when organizations provide high-quality healthcare for

their employees (social sustainability), there are fewer chances that the organizations will lose workforce capacity [49].

Resilience is the ability or property to absorb or to face to disturbance in way to avoid permanent breakdown and to recover in reasonable time. The term Resilience is often associated with the term Sustainability. “A resilient system can adjust its functioning before, during, or following changes and disturbances, so that it can continue to perform as required after a disruption or major mishap, and in presence of continuous stresses” [50]. The Figure 3 illustrates resilience as a component of sustainability [49].

Figure 3: Resilience as a component of sustainability

In other words, Figure 3 shows how a resilient system can become sustainable after recovery from a disturbance.

Resilience can be analysed separately as well. Figure 4 describes the process of a disruptive event in a supply chain, which is also applicable to inland waterway transport. Before an event, the IWT system is preparing itself during **Pre-Disruption Phase**. The occurrence of a disruptive event leads to a significant performance drop in the IWT system. During the **Disruption Phase**, the IWT system responds to the event and later recovers from the disruption. Finally, the IWT system adapts and reaches the old performance level during the **Post-Disruption Phase**.

Figure 4: Supply Chain Resilience Phases (Author based on Sheffi 2007)

Any serious disruption will follow a typical process with several phases where the IWT system performance is affected [51], [52].

Pre-Disruption Phase: During the Pre-Disruption Phase the IWT actors should be **prepared** for any disruption. This includes monitoring the IWT system for risks [51].

Disruptive Event: A serious event takes place such as a supplier getting bankrupt, a strike, or an extreme weather event occurs. These events are mostly external and have often dramatic consequences [52].

During-disruption: At first, companies try to control the situation to prevent further consequences. This first **response** to the disruption could also lead to shutting down affected systems. After an initial impact, the extent can increase during this phase, depending on the type of event and the vulnerability of the IWT system. However, when the impact of the event reaches its maximum, the performance of the IWT system drops significantly. Usually, preparations for **recovery** start in parallel with the first response and sometimes even preceding the disruptive event, if it has been expected. The **recovery** includes measures to return to normal operations, which could lead to higher-than-normal utilization [52].

Post-Disruption Phase: Recovery after a disruption usually takes time. IWT system resilience offers the opportunity to learn from a disruptive event, and to **adapt** in order to reach a higher level afterward. In this phase, other stakeholders may be selected, processes revised, and software systems improved [52].

4.3 Key Performance Indicators

Events such as low- or high-water periods in IWT may cause long-lasting interruptions to the corresponding transport chains. In this respect, stakeholders involved in IWT need to carry out numerous navigational and planning decisions [48]. There are various business management tools and approaches, and defining KPIs is one of the most common and effective ways of managing business processes used by organizations [53]. KPIs may be defined as “quantifiable (metric) aspects that reflect key factors that organizations must monitor and manage” and can portray the current scenario of an organization [51]. The KPIs relevant to ReNEW can be divided into several categories. Some KPIs assess sustainability and resilience and can directly be assigned to the areas of sustainability and resilience.

Furthermore, there exist other KPIs, such as operational KPIs, KPIs for service quality, and resource utilization KPIs, which can be assigned to either or both of the domains or form a subdomain. These are initially referred to as “other KPIs”. The specific assignment is then made in the course of the project and the context of the results from the LL.

Which KPIs are relevant also depends heavily on the perspective of the companies/organizations/stakeholders involved. For example, different KPIs are more relevant for a barge operator than for a port authority or a company located in the port.

Nearly all KPIs are affected by an event that causes disruptions and interruptions. This includes, for example, KPIs that measure the time it takes to carry out transport, the greater the interruption, the longer the transport takes and the results of the KPI “Transit time” are correspondingly poor.

The majority of research focuses on resilience and sustainability KPIs in general, supply chains, or specific industries. A lack of research providing a comprehensive overview of resilience and sustainability KPIs in the IWT is highlighted. To provide a better understanding of resilience and sustainability KPIs that can be applied to the IWT, a combination of different methodologies has been used, as shown in Figure 5. First, a literature review has been conducted, considering the sources dealing with the aforementioned KPIs in general, supply chain in general, and transport in general. This step was very important, given that draft KPIs which can be applied to IWT were identified. In this respect, various sources have been considered such as scientific papers, reports, and white papers. In addition to the literature review itself, research results from other projects in IWT, mostly Innovation-driven Collaborative European Inland Waterways Transport Network (IW-NET) project [54] and NSW (National Single Window)-Plus project [55]) were also applied.

Figure 5: Research steps

After drafting the KPIs, consultations were held with other experts involved in the project. A special focus was on the experts who are responsible for the ReNEW project Living Labs. In the LLs, ReNEW results will be tested and demonstrated, including Living Labs #1 – #4¹. In this respect, this deliverable represents the first step of the project, according to which the solutions will be developed and the results will be tested.

Before defining Sustainability and Resilience KPIs, it is necessary to consider the expected impact and indicators toward topic outcomes from the GA:

- Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.
- Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human-caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at the network level during disruptions.
- Contribute with at least a 20% increase in the modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.
- Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.
- Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%. For example, the boats (like LL1's) are built in aluminum and are therefore highly recyclable, as well as the materials for propulsion and ballast (except the batteries).

¹ Living Lab #1 – Ghent's Multifunctional Synchromodality City Logistics Hub
 • Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway management – DIW2024
 • Living Lab #3 – Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, in addition, to boosting modal shift
 • Living Lab #4 – Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

- Reduce environmental impact (emissions, soil/water pollution, degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats) during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.

4.3.1 Sustainability KPIs, Metrics and Measures

Sustainability consists of three aspects: economic, environmental and social aspects. Economic sustainability may be achieved by producing various goods and providing services in a responsible manner [56]. *Economic KPIs* may be the following:

- Total cost (transport, handling, waiting times, etc.)
- Waiting time costs (in port or at a lock)
- The total profit obtained in the transport
- Transport cost (fuel consumption, staff costs, etc.) (IW-NET project [54]) and
- Cost of cargo handling (loading and unloading)
- State of Fairway engineering structures (availability, rehabilitation, maintenance, replacement)
- Bridge clearance
- State of floating marks
- Market share
- ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival)
- Load capacity/water level
- Loading and unloading capacity
- Loading time
- Storage capacity

The environmental sustainability aspect refers to the ability to maintain the quality and reproducibility of natural resources [56]. According to Hristov et al. [57] and based on IW-NET [54] results, *Environmental/ecological KPIs* are the following:

- Use of returnable containers [57]
- Total direct or indirect emissions of greenhouse gases by weight [57]
- Reduced CO₂ emissions per fleet [57]
- Renewable sources rate [57]
- Waste reduction rate [57]
- Efficiency resources use rate [57]
- Reduced fuel energy (IW-NET project)
- Use of returnable containers [57]
- Percentage of reusable/ recycled material [57]
- The intensity of greenhouse gases emissions (kg CO₂/km...) or Reduced environmental impact [CO₂e] (GA)
- Habitat status
- Indigenous and exogenous species status (Faunal and floral examinations)

- Pollution rate (air, water, noise, soil)
- Water velocity
- Erosion state (hydrological and morphological aspects)
- Sedimentation state (hydrological and morphological aspects)
- Fairway depth and width
- Minimum bridge clearance
- Water discharge
- Water level
- Sedimentation (considering infrastructures)
- Sediment quantification (considering infrastructures)
- Erosion (considering infrastructures)

Some KPIs fall into both economic and environmental aspects, such as:

- ROI related to environmental protection [57]
- % of investments in environmental technology [57]
- % additional revenue (due to recycling etc.) [57]
- Empty containers transported [57]
- Load capacity/water level
- Accommodation capacity for vessels
- Improved navigability capacity (GA)
- Increase in modal shift (GA)
- Material fatigue (Based on life cycle)

The social sustainability aspect contributes not only to business goals, but also to the greater well-being, stability, and success of the surrounding society [56].

KPIs from the social aspect are [58], [59]:

- Employee training
- Average employee overtime hours
- Integration rate
- Employee attendance rates
- Stakeholder's satisfaction rate
- Customer satisfaction rate
- Employee satisfaction rate
- Social initiatives at the national and local levels
- The average age of employees (attractiveness)

There are KPIs that fall into both economic and social aspects, such as:

- Health and safety prevention costs
- The smooth functioning of passenger mobility (GA)

Some KPIs fall into both environmental/ecological and social aspects, such as *thresholds of pollution (air and water) and noise disturbance (well-being of neighbourhood and habitat)*.

4.3.2 Resilience KPIs, Metrics and Measures

In order to define the resilience Key Performance Indicators first, the driving enablers of resilience have to be defined. These enablers are also called principles or capabilities. Ali, A. et al. [60] joined all these terms and called them elements. After the definition of these elements, indicators have to be defined to measure the performance of each element. These indicators can be used as resilience KPIs.

Security

Security focuses on protecting companies against disruptions related to intended attacks, i.e., cyber-attacks or physical attacks. Ali, A. et al. [60] describes several mitigation measures to cope with these disruptions. Consequently, the resilience element *Security* can be measured by the implementation of the resilience KPI *Security measures against threats*. This contains the identification of vulnerabilities in the security domain, the assessment of risks and the implementation of appropriate mitigation measures. However, after analyzing the results of other projects such as IW-NET [54] and NSW-Plus project [55] and an additional literature review, additional KPIs, measures and metrics were identified. In this respect, *Security* may be observed also through the following KPIs. One of them is *IT Systems Sustain/Recovery Attack*. For this KPI, the following measures and metrics can be used:

- Mean time between downtime/failures: How many days have passed since a system failure? If there is a long time between system failures, this means that the systems under consideration are highly reliable. (NSW-Plus project) [55]
- Percentage difference in downtime/failure: Do some system operations experience more failures in a specified period of time than other system operations? Depending on the frequency and severity of the failures, remediation may be necessary. (NSW-Plus project) [55]
- Average repair time: How many hours does it take on average to fix a problem and restore full functionality? If it takes too long to fix a malfunction, personnel and resources may need to be checked. (NSW-Plus project) [55]
- Percentage difference in repair time: Is there a percentage change in the time required to reboot systems? If it is always possible to return to regular operation more quickly than before, this shows that problems were resolved more quickly. (NSW-Plus project) [55]
- Progress of work to implement a backup solution for critical technologies [55]

Another KPI related to *Security* element is *IT Systems Availability* which may be measured as follows:

- System availability: If upstream systems were not available to be accessed, there may be a data accessibility issue that needs to be addressed. For example, to calculate this KPI, the

number of minutes that all systems were available to everyone can be divided by the number of minutes that the systems should be available. (NSW-Plus project) [55]

- Percentage of downtime due to planned activities: This is the time spent on necessary system maintenance, for example. To calculate this, the number of minutes spent on system maintenance can be divided by the number of minutes in a specified period. The aim of a KPI in this area is to check the time for planned maintenance work and optimize it in the long term. (NSW-Plus project) [55]
- The proportion of critical technologies hosted on the cloud [61]

Further KPIs that could be related to Security element are:

- Number of security incidents (e.g., hijackings, piracy, sabotage)
- Number of security breaches (e.g., unauthorized access to vessels or facilities)
- Number of security inspections and audits passed

Safety

Another identified resilience element is *Safety* since *Safety* is essential to ensure smooth operations. Some of the *Safety* KPIs are:

- Lost time injury frequency rate (the number of lost time injuries that occurred in a specific period) [62]
- The number of actions to address health and safety issues
- Total number of reported incidents
- The severity of accidents or incidents
- The frequency of equipment breakdowns
- Number of accidents or incidents per year

Knowledge Management

In knowledge management, knowledge has to be captured, structured, reused, and improved. For the supply chain resilience domain, knowledge management is especially important after disruption for the assessment of the “supplier delivery efficiency” for keeping or changing suppliers. A similar method can be applied to other supply chain partners [51].

For this element, the resilience KPI *Knowledge Management* is used which comprises the entire process featuring capturing, structuring, reusing, and improving knowledge. Several measures and metrics can be used: *Percentage of use of knowledge resources*, *Frequency of knowledge updates* (average time between updates), or *Amount of resolved incidents due to particular knowledge*.

Visibility

Supply Chain Visibility enables supply chain actors to monitor their assets, like vessels, trucks, containers, and also cargo [63]. Detailed information on the current status of the transport can be used to issue proactive alerts to mitigate disruptive impacts [51]. For this element, the KPI *Information Level* describes whether all assets can be monitored. The resilience KPI *Quality of data* considers where the data is coming from (directly from the source or aggregated by additional data providers) and if it is in real-time [64]. For example, some of metrics and measures that are related to Quality of data are: *Number of errors* (dividing the total number of errors by the total number of items) [65] and *Number of empty values* [65] which indicate the information is missing from a data set.

Information Sharing

According to Kim et al. [66], information sharing in supply chains can be defined as “the degree to which supply chain members exchange relevant and timely information and knowledge, including production, demand, and inventory data, as well as the exchange of best practices and innovations.”

Information sharing can have different aspects, including formal and informal communication, the use of common information systems, and collaboration in decision-making. It is often eased by communication technology, such as electronic data interchange (EDI) systems.

KPI *Communication technology* describes the type of technology which is used for information exchange. This can range from telephone calls, fax, and unstructured emails to EDI interfaces. In addition, the KPI *Organizational culture* describes the degree of openness and transparency to share information an organization has. Other KPIs that could be used are also: *Degree to which stakeholders exchange relevant and timely information and knowledge* [66], and *Time spent searching for information and time spent on repetitive tasks* [67].

Trust

As already presented, companies that share information with other actors in the supply chain have increased visibility and can work more efficiently than others. A prerequisite is to have trust among all partners, which enables cooperation, conflict reduction and facilitates improved decision-making during disturbances in the chain [63]. In order to assess the element of Trust, the resilience KPI *Level of Trust* can be used, which describes the trust in other partners of the supply chain. This contains how intense and lasting the cooperation between the partners in different areas is, like information sharing, sharing of knowledge and cooperative decision-making. The following metrics and measures can be used to measure the *Level of trust* such as [68]:

- Percent increase in employee satisfaction and trust score
- Percent reduction in employee turnover rate
- Percent increase in repeat customers
- Percent reduction in legal fees
- Percent decrease in lawsuits or complaints filed

Risk Management

According to (Christopher & Peck) [63] Risk Management is an important element of supply chain resilience because many risks cannot be anticipated or avoided. Proper Risk Management enables the reduction of vulnerabilities and the impact of consequences by identification, assessment, monitoring of risks and implementing suitable mitigation strategies. For the assessment of this element of resilience, the following KPIs can be used: *Identification of risks*, *Assessment of risks* and *Implementation of Mitigation Measures* and *Costs of risk management programs*. The following metric and measures can be used for this element:

- Number of identified risks [69]
- Number of risks that occurred per year [69]
- Percentage of risks monitored per year [69]
- Percentage of risks mitigated per year [69]
- Probability of occurrence in the future by taking a specific time period in the past (e.g., 1 year or 5 years or 10 years)
- Impact strengths resulting from consequences (none, low, medium, high)

Robustness

Scholten et al. [70] claim that *robustness* supports companies to continue business operations by being resistant to any serious disruption. Robust Supply Chains can absorb unforeseen shocks and cut down the impact of a disruption.

The following KPIs are related to *robustness*: *On Time Delivery* and *Amount of cargo, vessels and back-up equipment to be reallocated due to failure*. Furthermore, *Vessel and equipment running time between two failures* and *Vessel and equipment repair time* may be used to measure the Robustness element.

Collaboration

Agreeing with Ali et al. [60] “[...] collaboration is the ability to respond to supply chain disruptions with partners through collaborative planning and information- and knowledge-sharing to coordinate the immediate response”. A strong collaboration of actors in a supply chain can undoubtedly facilitate a reduction of risks. There are a few related KPIs. The first KPI is *Time of response* (time to fulfill the request). Fast response time is generally considered a positive indication of effective collaboration [71]. Another KPI is *Partner’s reliability* calculated on a basis of the average failure rate of services provided by partner [71]. Furthermore, the following measures and metrics can be used to measure the aforementioned resilience element: *Number of provided services* [71], *Number of involved partners* [71] and *Number of partners with the same competence* [71].

Flexibility

Flexibility describes the skill to face a growing diversity of customer expectations. In contrast to Agility, Flexibility is dealing with predictable changes [51].

Agility

The ability to respond quickly to changes is characterized by Agility. In contrast to Flexibility, Agility covers unpredictable changes which represent mostly external events with dramatic impact [51]. Reducing lead time, both for orders and deliveries, can lead to improved supply chain response time and increased customer satisfaction, according to studies by Karl, A. et al. [51]. Consequently, the resilience KPI *Lead time* can be used in order to measure Supply Chain Agility.

As *Agility* and *Flexibility* are very similar, they can be measured with the same KPIs. For example, one of the KPIs is *Lead time*. A short lead time indicates that the transport process is fast and leads to improved (supply chain) response time. Another related KPI is *Total transit time*, which measures overall efficiency of the transportation process; a short transit time indicates that the transport process is fast and meets the needs of customers [54]. The last related KPI is *On time delivery rate and time required for loading and unloading cargo from the vessel*. In order to obtain such KPIs, it is possible to take into account metrics such as *Waiting time* [54] and *Failure rate*, which means that the transportation system has frequent failures, which reduces its agility or flexibility [71].

Redundancy

Adding additional capacity in terms of production, transportation, inventory and storage facilities improves the redundancy of the supply chain. These supplementary resources can replace losses rapidly during unexpected events [63]. As adding additional capacity improves the redundancy of the transport system and supply chain, the following KPIs can be used: *Number of backup vessels or equipment*, *Alternative routes* (the degree to which an organization used multiple routes to transport cargo or passengers), and *Alternative transport modes* in case of certain disruptions.

Rapidity (~ Responsiveness)

The ability to react or to deploy a solution within the agreed period. For example, *ETA (Estimated time to arrive)* may represent one of the KPIs for rapidity of travel. The resilience element *Rapidity* may have also other KPIs: *On-time delivery rate*, *Shortest route distance* (IW-NET project [54]), *Total average speed* (IW-NET project [54]), *Transit time* (IW-NET project [54]), *Total number of operating services* (IW-NET project [54]), *Load/unload time*, etc. Certain metrics and measures can be used such as *Transit time*, *Distance and the number of stops*, etc.

Resourcefulness

Resourcefulness may be defined as the capacity to make the appropriate budget available, identify problems, establish priorities, and mobilize resources after a certain event [72], [73] and consists of KPIs such as *Vessel capacity utilization*, *Maintenance and repair costs*, *Number of vehicles and equipment in use*, etc.

4.3.3 Other KPIs

Although KPIs can be categorized into different categories, sometimes these categories are interrelated. Several KPIs could help organizations in IWT to understand the business process as well as its gaps, which is a prerequisite for a business to be optimal. For example, if a cargo needs more time for transportation, this can lead to high costs, and costs fall under the economic aspect of sustainability (sustainable KPI). In this respect, there are several KPIs covering operational KPIs, resource utilization KPIs and Quality of service KPIs. All of these KPIs can be as well allocated to the area of sustainability KPIs as well as to resilience KPIs.

Although the differentiation of KPIs into the areas of sustainability and resilience has only been taking place for a few years, KPIs have been established in the maritime sector since 2006. The BIMCO Shipping KPI Standard published by The Baltic and International Maritime Council (BIMCO) already exists in version 4.0 with the last update in September 2020, version 5.0 is currently in preparation.

The Shipping KPI Standard is built up hierarchically with 3 different levels:

- Key Performance Indicators groups (KPI groups)
- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
- Performance Indicators (PIs)

The last two levels have a mathematical relationship. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are calculated from Performance Indicators (the lowest level) using a KPI formula². On the most basic level, there are 63 PIs that are based on data capture (measurements or counters) directly from a ship

² For example: **Budget performance**

This KPI expresses the overall budget deviation. The KPI reflects the company's ability effectively plan the ship's operating costs. It does not value the cost effectiveness. Deviations both positive and negative are regarded in the same way.

Calculation Period	Fiscal year
Scope	Ship level
Unit	%

KPI Value Formula:

(using 3 Performance Indicators)

PI010 Last year's AAE (Additional Authorized Expenses)

PI011 Last year's actual running costs and accruals

PI012 Last year's running cost budget

$$KPI\ value = \frac{|PI012 - (PI011 - PI010)|}{PI012}$$

Based on the amounts stated for the above Performance Indicators the percentile rank by comparing KPI value against other ships with the same criteria will be calculated.

BIMCO, The Shipping KPI Standard V4.0 ,page 15, <https://shipping-kpi.org/documentation>
<https://shipping-kpi.org/?code=404>

or from shipping management. To reduce the amount of data, data is collected once and re-used within the Shipping KPI Standard. The 33 KPIs are rated on a scale of 0-100, with zero indicating poor performance and 100 indicating exceptional performance. This allows the comparison of ships with varying characteristics or amounts of data captured. Here are some examples from the BIMCO Shipping KPI Standard that might be of relevance for ReNEW [74], [75]:

- Ballast water management violations
- Cargo related incidents
- Drydocking planning performance
- Failure of critical equipment and systems

These KPIs – among others – will be examined further in the course of the project and examined in particular with regard to their relevance for LL. In addition, relevant KPIs will be assigned to the areas of sustainability and resilience.

4.3.4 First Selection of KPIs relevant for the ReNEW Living Labs

In addition to the KPIs that are specifically relevant for the individual LL, there are some KPIs that are defined in the GA and must be taken into account for all LL.

- Improved navigability capacity: This refers to the ability to move around a particular area more easily and efficiently. For example, a Living Lab might focus on improving the navigability of a city's streets by implementing smarter traffic management systems, better public transportation options, or more effective pedestrian and bike lanes.
- Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience: This refers to the ability of an area's physical infrastructure to withstand and recover from natural or man-made disasters, such as floods, earthquakes, or cyberattacks. A Living Lab might focus on improving infrastructure resilience by implementing more robust building materials, better emergency response systems, or more secure information technology systems.
- Increase in modal shift: This refers to a change in the way goods are transported or people travel, such as moving from driving alone to carpooling or taking public transportation. Against the background of ReNEW a Living Lab might focus on increasing modal shift by implementing more efficient transportation options, or promoting forms of transportation with alternative propulsion systems.
- Smooth functioning of passenger mobility: This refers to the ability of people to move around a particular area without experiencing significant delays or disruptions. A Living Lab might focus on improving passenger mobility by implementing smarter traffic management systems, better public transportation options, or more effective pedestrian and bike lanes.
- Reduce environmental impact [CO₂e]: This refers to the amount of greenhouse gas emissions produced by a particular area or activity, which contribute to climate change. A Living Lab might focus on reducing environmental impact by promoting sustainable transportation options, implementing energy-efficient buildings and infrastructure, or promoting behavior changes like reducing waste and conserving resources.

Living Lab #1 - Ghent's Multifunctional Synchronodality City Logistics Hub

According to the GA and the described use cases for LL1 some potential KPIs for evaluating the impact of climate disasters on the infrastructure resilience, and readiness in setting up emergency plans might be of relevance. These KPIs should help to assess the ability of the city's infrastructure to withstand and recover from natural disasters, and the effectiveness of emergency plans in protecting the population and minimizing damage to critical infrastructure. Additionally, these KPIs should enable the city to identify areas for improvement and make informed decisions about allocating resources to enhance resilience and preparedness.

For each type of risk (natural, technological, health, and safety risks), specific KPIs may need to be developed to evaluate the impact of disasters on infrastructure resilience and emergency response.

Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway management – DIW2024

For LL 2 the focus of relevant KPIs might focus on the overall performance of the Douro river transportation system in terms of safety, security, environmental protection, and navigation efficiency. They should also enable the identification of areas for improvement and the implementation of targeted measures to enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of the system.

Living Lab #3 - Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, and in addition to boost modal shift

For LL3, which focuses on planning a mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, and to boost modal shift, the potential key performance indicators that could be relevant should help to evaluate the success of LL3 in promoting climate resilience and environmental sustainability in transport infrastructure and boosting modal shift towards sustainable transport options. They would also enable the identification of areas for improvement and the implementation of targeted measures to enhance the effectiveness and impact of the mitigation demonstrator app.

Living Lab #4 – Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

For LL4, KPIs which would help to evaluate the success of LL4 in promoting resilience through autonomous, zero-emission barges are important. They would enable the identification of areas for improvement and the implementation of targeted measures to enhance the effectiveness and impact of the autonomous barges in reducing emissions, promoting resilience, and ensuring economic viability.

4.4 Cost Benefit Analysis

At present, no information is available on the costs and benefits for ReNEW, so as a first step only a theoretical consideration of a CBA and a presentation of the proposed approach is given here.

A cost-benefit analysis is an instrument to determine whether a result - the benefit - of an action or measure justifies the effort required for it - the costs. If it can be assumed that benefits and costs are not certain to occur, their expected values, i.e., benefits or costs weighted by their assumed probabilities of occurrence, are used. In the case of the present assessment relevant to ReNEW, the latter is the possible frequency with which the 'disruption' scenarios linked to the LLs could occur.

In general, a cost benefit analysis is based on welfare theory, which states that the goal of each measure is supposed to maximize total welfare to the national society. It can be viewed as a rational and systematic system for assessing actions by expressing all potential consequences in a directly comparable unit of measurement - money. All costs and benefits are managed in the same particular way [76].

Definition of Costs

Costs are expenses related to the purchase of inputs such as capital equipment, buildings, materials, labour, and public utilities [77]. External costs such as environmental damage or health risks are often described as negative externalities [78].

- Construction costs; including costs for material and installation resulting in total manufacturing costs
- Investment costs
- Maintenance costs are the labour and material costs associated with servicing, repair, modification, restoration, inspection, testing, and troubleshooting tasks
- Operating costs; refers to all costs incurred, such as daily rental rates, labour costs, and transportation costs (crew and equipment)
- Insurance costs

Definition of Benefits

Although it can be vague, the term « Benefit » has a strong connection with the preferences of some stakeholders, groups, etc. In a cost-benefit analysis, it is often difficult to directly measure the benefit in monetary terms. But each disruption leads to an increase in costs, avoiding the disruption or mitigating the effects of that disruption results in fewer costs, which can then be classified as a benefit. For example, in the context of the restoration of biodiversity damage, the benefits of a restoration option are equal to the 'avoided' damage to biodiversity (both initial damage and interim losses). Just as damage is assessed in relation to the baseline condition of the damaged resource, benefits should be measured in relation to the same baseline. This is referred to as 'with/without principle' of cost-benefit analysis [78], [79], [80], [81].

Various methodologies can be used to determine the value of benefits, but in order to choose the most adequate one, the following should be taken into account.

Which methodology to use often depends on the availability of relevant prices as well as on the time and expense of the analysis. For example, to calculate the total amount of benefits the following methods can be applied [82]:

- Market Price Method [83], [84]: this method calculates the economic values of ecosystem products or services purchased and sold in commercial markets (e.g. a cultural site could be valued based on the entrance fees collected).
- Productivity Method [85]: Economic values for ecosystem products or services that play a role in manufacturing commercially marketed goods are evaluated in this case (e.g. the benefits of different levels of water quality improvement will be compared to the cost of reductions in polluting runoff).
- Hedonic Pricing Method [86]: measures the economic values for ecosystem or environmental services that directly affect market prices of other goods (e.g. the variations in housing prices, which reflect the value of local environmental attributes).
- Travel Cost Method [87]: this method evaluates the economic values associated with ecosystems or sites which are used for recreation. The value of the site is reflected in how much people are willing to pay to travel to this site.
- Damage Cost Avoided, Replacement Cost, and Substitute Cost Methods [88]: These methods assess economic values by calculating the costs of avoided damages caused by lost ecosystem services, the costs of replacing ecosystem services, or the costs of providing substitute services (e.g., costs avoided by providing flood protection).
- Contingent Valuation Method [89]: estimates economic values for virtually any ecosystem or environmental service, it is the commonly used method to assess non-use or passive use values (e.g. the willingness to pay to protect a particular area).

Cost-benefit analysis provides several decision criteria to determine whether an investment is worthwhile or not. These include, for example, the internal rate of return or the internal rate of return on capital and the payback period.

The internal rate of return is the return or profitability of a measure – e.g., a measure for improving resilience- based on a discounted cash flow analysis. The internal rate of return (IRR) is the interest rate that is applied within a certain period to achieve a net present value (NPV) of zero [90].

In the case of an investment, capital is tied up which is then available in the form of the investment and not as a monetary value and thus cannot be used for other purposes. This quasi-lost profit from the otherwise possible "productive" use of the amount is taken into account, for example, with calculative interest for the tied-up capital. It thus reflects the interest rate that an investor could have earned by investing the money on the capital market or that he can expect for the use of his money. The amount resulting from discounting is called the net present value, or present value. ISL has applied calculative interest rates of 2% to a maximum of 4% in previous CBAs.

Another decision criterion is the payback period (PP), which is the time it takes for the cumulative present value of benefits to become equal to the cumulative present value of costs [91].

For a cost-benefit analysis, it is useful to distinguish between two situations: On the one hand, the situation without the occurrence of damage - the strategic level - in which the measures have been implemented, but only in order to be prepared for the occurrence of damage. On the other hand, the situation of the occurrence of damage - the tactical level - includes the associated reactions or activities.

The strategic level determines what needs to be done to be prepared for the next 10 years, for example, i.e., the implementation of individual measures. Depending on whether this requires the purchase of certain things, the relevant cost elements for this level would be the acquisition costs and the annual costs incurred for maintenance measures. For example, this could be the cost of purchasing security software to defend against cyberattacks. If necessary, the extent of the damage can be estimated based on the KPIs already defined, thereby determining the costs incurred as a result of the damage.

Regarding the tactical level, all costs incurred in response to a damage event are relevant. These can be, for example, the labour input to rectify the damage event, as well as the lost revenue due to interruptions in the transport process.

The hazard and vulnerability scenario catalogue described in Section 3 is intended to provide a basis for analysing the current risks and costs to IWT should the described disruptions occur. Against this background, potential risks from adverse events or disasters that could affect IWT can be assessed.

In ReNEW - for the collection of hazards and vulnerabilities for the corresponding catalogue - a distinction is made between likelihood and frequency. The likelihood was subdivided as follows:

- A – Rare
- B – Unlikely
- C – Probable
- D – Likely
- E – Certain

If the frequency of occurrence of the loss event varies, the costs in the loss event change overall. This means that the resulting benefit is an expected value since it is weighted by the probability of occurrence.

Regarding the frequency, the corresponding categories for the probability of occurrence per year still have to be defined. Initially, the following is assumed. However, this can still change in the course of the project based on the empirical values from the LL.³

- 0: impossible
- 1: not to be expected (once in 5-20 years) - 1 damage event within 20 years (probability of occurrence 0.05 per year)
- 2: rare (once in 3-5 years) - 1 loss event every 5 years, (probability of occurrence 0.2 per year)
- 3: occasionally (once a year) - 1 loss event per year, (probability of occurrence 1 per year)
- 4: Frequently (several times a year) - 5 loss events per year, (probability of occurrence 5 per year)
- 5: regularly (monthly) - 12 incidents per year (probability of occurrence 12 per year), (probability of occurrence 12 per year)

The impossible probability of occurrence categorised as "0" will usually not be taken into account in the calculations. Regarding the identification of benefits, the focus of the cost-benefit analysis carried out here is on the avoidance or reduction of costs that occur in the event of damage. The expected benefit - like the costs - is measured in monetary units to enable comparability and offsetting.

In the case of ReNEW, it is assumed that an investment is only a kind of insurance to improve resilience with regard to any damage that may occur. As a result, the costs that arise in the event of damage are examined. The measures to improve resilience should result in damage remaining at a low level or, in the best case, not occurring at all, thus reducing or eliminating damage costs. These reduced/eliminated damage costs are then classified as benefits.

Against this background, the project will analyse the impacts of implementing different resilience strategies and identify the most cost-effective resilience strategies that can be implemented in the inland navigation sector.

Depending on the cost data available, a calculation model can be created for the result presentation that combines the strategic with the tactical information for different scenarios. For a more flexible calculation, there are various input and selection fields for defining the criteria, such as input fields for the calculated interest rate and selection fields for choosing the frequency of the damage event. Since the calculation of costs and benefits is done on a theoretical level, no information is available when the damage event occurs. For this reason, both the costs in the event of damage and the benefits are multiplied by the possible frequency of the occurrence of damage - related to a specific time period. The calculated probabilities of occurrence are used for the calculation. The calculation model also offers the possibility of changing the downtimes of affected systems and can then show

³ The probability of occurrence is calculated by dividing the number of damage events by the number of years.

the results for the net present value, the payback period, and the internal rate of return on capital, taking into account the possible occurrence probabilities of the damage events [76].

In all scenarios to be developed, it is assumed that no people are harmed. Although some publications classify the statistical value of human life, evaluating and integrating this into a cost-benefit analysis would exceed the specified scope of the project. Furthermore, it is assumed that every company has public liability insurance that covers possible personal injuries.

5 Building Blocks and Data Sources

According to the GA, building blocks are to be provided that serve as a basis for the planning, operation, evaluation and impact assessment of Floating Modular Platforms, autonomous inland vessels, the digital twins as well as the benchmarking of emission-neutral solutions.

Depending on the requirements from the LL, this list of building blocks and data sources will be continuously updated, extended and specified during the course of the project.

Specifications, analyses, tools, and models from various projects will serve as candidates for building blocks that will be extended, adapted, and configured according to the specific functional, geographic, or process requirements of ReNEW.

In addition, data sources will be identified, analyzed, and linked, and will serve as the basis for the models and simulation tools and assessment of ReNEW LL sustainability and resilience scenarios and measures.

Building Blocks can be data sources as well as contain data sources. To provide some differentiation, the following section presents Building Blocks in the form of analyses, methods, models, catalogues, ontologies, etc., and the detailed information where relevant data can be found in the section for Data Sources.

5.1 Building Blocks

In this section the first release of Building Blocks will be presented. Table 8 gives an overview, by using the link the descriptions can be reached.

Table 8: Overview of Building Blocks

Building Blocks	
Analyses/Catalogues	5.1.1
AI based models	5.1.2
Methodology	5.1.3
Models	5.1.4
Simulation based models	5.1.5
Tools	5.1.6
Vessel Route Planner	5.1.7

5.1.1 Analyses/Catalogues

Resilience strategies

Catalogues were created during the project BRESilient, by using desk research, interviews with relevant stakeholders and three workshops with experts from the logistics domain. One workshop featured a specially designed serious game in order to develop and discuss adaptation measures.

- Catalogue of extreme weather events and their impact in the domain of maritime logistics and hinterland transport, incl. IWT, truck and train.
- Catalogue of adaption measures for different stakeholders against extreme weather events.

Possible Extension within ReNEW:

- Further specification resilience strategies for IWT and hinterland transport
- Climate adaptation measures to increase resilience

<https://bresilient.de/>

5.1.2 AI Based Models

Water level forecasting

public

Estimating the level of water in rivers can be extremely useful in places prone to flooding. While traditional methods are mostly based on physical models, another alternative is gaining traction: artificial neural networks. Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent Neural Networks underpin the model.

<https://github.com/kalisio/water-level-forecasting>

5.1.3 Methodology

IWT Modelling Capabilities

Capability and library to simulate IW traffic flows and networks. Within the IW-NET project (www.iw-net.eu), existing models have been implemented by ISL and ITAINOVA using the AnyLogic environment. One of the IW-NET application scenarios is the simulation of traffic flow optimization strategies for locks and narrow fairway sections on river Weser and Mittelland Canal, e.g. priority rules for larger IWT vessels.

Possible Extension within ReNEW:

- Consideration of changes in navigational conditions on certain fairway sections, e.g., low water, which may lead to restrictions and limitations
- Configuration of other geographical situations and management strategies

www.iw-net.eu

(Geo)data Visualization and Provision Capabilities

Toolchain and capability to visualize and provide (geospatial) data using modern web services/ interfaces (M2M/GUI).

Possible Extension within ReNEW:

(Map) visualization of

- Potential bottlenecks and risk areas, hazards
- ReNEW resilience index
- Consideration and provision of ReNEW data using unified REST API (developed in IW-NET)

www.iw-net.eu

5.1.4 Models

Cost-Benefit-Analysis (CBA) Model

For several projects ISL created a CBA calculation model for the presentation of CBA results that combines the strategic with the tactical information for different scenarios. For a more flexible calculation, there are various input and selection fields for defining the criteria, such as input fields for the calculated interest rate and selection fields for choosing the frequency of the damage event. Since the calculation of costs and benefits is done on a theoretical level, no information is available when the damage event occurs. For this reason, both the costs in the event of damage and the benefits are multiplied by the possible frequency of the occurrence of damage - related to a specific time period. The calculated probabilities of occurrence are used for the calculation. The calculation model also offers the possibility of changing the downtimes of affected systems. It can then show the results for the net present value, the payback period and the internal rate of return on capital, taking into account the possible occurrence probabilities of the damage events.

This model can be adapted focusing on the requirements of ReNEW LL in order to carry out a CBA. The results will be available in Excel format."

Source: ISL

Ontology for Simulation

The ReNEW project partner ITA – as well involved in IW-NET - created an ontology where the data used in the IW-NET simulation and their relationships are presented. This ontology will be matched with the information from the simulations developed by ISL and a common, consolidated ontology will be created. The result can then also serve as a building block for the simulations to be created in ReNEW.

Source: ITA, ISL

5.1.5 Simulation based models

OpenCLSim

public

OpenCLSim (OpenCLSim) is a software for rule-driven scheduling of cyclic operations that allows for in-depth comparison of various operating strategies.

<https://openclsim.readthedocs.io/>

HiPIMS

public

High-Performance Integrated Hydrodynamic Modelling System (HiPIMS) standards. It solves the 2D shallow water equations for flood simulations using cutting-edge numerical techniques (Godunov-type finite volume). HiPIMS is implemented on several GPUs (Graphics Processing Units) utilizing the CUDA/C++ languages to provide high-resolution flood simulations. HiPIMS has the potential to be further improved for various applications in hydrological research due to its modular and adaptable structure, as long as the problem can be handled on a consistent rectangular grid..

<https://github.com/HEMLab/hipims>

HEC-HMS	public
<p>The Hydrologic Modelling System (HEC-HMS) simulates the entire hydrologic processes of dendritic watershed systems. Many standard hydrologic analysis processes, including as event infiltration, unit hydrographs, and hydrologic routing, are included in the software. HEC-HMS also offers continuous modeling techniques such as evapo-transpiration, snowmelt, and soil moisture accounting. Advanced capabilities for gridded runoff simulation employing the linear quasi-distributed runoff transform (ModClark) are also offered. Model optimization, forecasting streamflow, depth-area reduction, analyzing model uncertainty, erosion and sediment transport, and water quality are all supported by additional analysis tools.</p>	
<p>https://www.hec.usace.army.mil/software/hec-hms/</p>	
iRIC	public
<p>The International River Interface Cooperative (iRIC) aims to developing a software platform called iRIC for numerical simulation of flow and morpho-dynamics in rivers.</p>	
<p>http://i-ric.org/en/</p>	
SOBEK	commercial
<p>A modeling package for flood forecasting, drainage system optimization, irrigation system control, sewage overflow design, river morphology, salt intrusion, and surface water quality.</p>	
<p>https://www.deltares.nl/en/software/sobek/</p>	
BIVAS (Binnenvaart Analyse Systeem)	commercial
<p>BIVAS is an inland shipping analysis system that was created to analyze the Dutch inland shipping network. It is intended to help researchers answer policy issues about:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. shipping network analysis: what is the usage of each waterway? 2. the impact of scheduled maintenance or obstructed waterways 3. developing future development scenarios 	
<p>https://bivas.chartasoftware.com/</p>	
<p>Modelling cascading effects</p>	
<p>Climate Change Impacts ASC interacting risks maps</p>	
<p>https://kumu.io/wspdigital/asc-interacting-risks-map#climate-change-impacts-flow-map/soil-desiccation</p>	

5.1.6 Tools

QGIS	public
QGIS is a cross-platform desktop geographic information system (GIS) application that is free and open source. It allows you to browse, modify, print, and analyze geographical data.	
https://qgis.org/en/site/	

Neo4J	public
Neo4j is a graph database management system. It offers different plugins such neosemantics which enables the use of RDF and its associated vocabularies like (OWL, RDFS, SKOS and others) in Neo4j.	
https://neo4j.com/labs/neosemantics/	

5.1.7 Vessel Route Planner

HALEM	public
Shipping route optimization software. It includes a route optimization technique for a given hydrodynamic model. Different routes that can be optimized are: shortest fastest, cheapest and cleanest route.	
https://halem.readthedocs.io	

5.2 Data Sources

The first release of Data Sources will be presented in this section. Table 9 provides an overview; descriptions can be accessed via the link.

Table 9: Overview of Data Sources

Data Sources	
Climate and Environmental Data	5.2.1
Databases	5.2.2
Maritime AIS Data	5.2.3
Waterways and Infrastructure Information	5.2.4
Other Data Sources	5.2.5

5.2.1 Climate and Environmental Data

Copernicus	public
Provide climate and environmental data about the past current and future to enable climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies.	
https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/toolbox	

Euro-Cordex	public (on request)
Provide regional climate change projections.	
https://cordex.org/data-access/	

Impactlab
Temperatures projections data; energy demand projections
https://impactlab.org/

5.2.2 Databases

Ship Engine Database

The ship engine database of ISL contains information on engines of seagoing vessels and contains already some information on inland vessels, but only on those calling at Hamburg and Bremen and not yet on auxiliary engines. The engine input parameters of all analysis types take into account the data of the main engines, the auxiliary engines as well as the boiler data (as far as technically given) as well as data on the fuel consumption of the respective consumption aggregates, the sulphur content of the fuel used and the type of fuel used. This information has already been used in various projects as a base for traffic simulation and calculation of vessel emissions and pollution (CO₂, SO_x, NO_x, PM). Depending on the requirements, the output of the evaluations will be in Excel format. Data can be made available by ISL.

Source: ISL

Transportation Network Data

Database with transportation network data including routing functionality. Network data is compiled using OpenStreetMap, Open Data provided by national or international organizations (such as RIS-index), and own desk research. The data cover major European corridors. The data are stored in Postgres DB. Data can be made available by ISL.

Network data includes e.g.

- Roads, rail and waterways (including infrastructures facilities)
- Ports/terminals/logistics hubs
- TEN-T network data (ISL maintains “TENtec” data in the MoS project)
- European container traffic model

Possible Extension within ReNEW:

- Extraction and abstraction of Inland ENC data
- Collection and localization of critical waterway sections/areas/risks/hazards
- AIS-based traffic data extraction (given AIS availability)

Source: ISL

5.2.3 Maritime AIS Data

Vesselfinder

commercial

API and databases of real-time and historical ship positions.

<https://www.vesselfinder.com/fr>

5.2.4 Waterways and Infrastructure Information

River Information Services (RIS)	public
<p>CESNI (European Committee for drawing up standards in the field of inland navigation) Access to a knowledge base for inland navigation information technology is given by this website, which is dedicated to River Information Service professionals. It includes information on Inland ECDIS (Inland Electronic Chart Display Information Service), ERI (Electronic Ship Reporting), NtS (Notices to Skippers), and VTT (Vessel Tracking and Tracing). "</p>	
<p>https://ris.cesni.eu/332-en.html</p>	
<p>EuRIS platform Enables access to information necessary for a skipper, vessel owner, or logistic operator on the main European waterways. (RIS-COMEX project [92])</p>	
<p>https://www.eurisportal.eu/</p>	
WFD reference spatial data sets	public
<p>The reference geographical data sets included in the Water Framework Directive (WFD) provide information about European river basin districts, river basin district sub-units, surface water bodies, groundwater bodies, and monitoring sites used in the first and second River Basin Management Plans (RBMP). The data sets are part of the Water Information System for Europe (WISE) and compile information provided to the European Commission (EC) and the European Environment Agency (EEA) by EU Member States, Norway, Iceland, and the United Kingdom since 2010.</p>	
<p>https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/wise-wfd-spatial</p>	
Waterway information of different European countries	public
Austria: Viadonau	https://www.viadonau.org/home
Belgium: De Vlaamse Waterweg	https://www.vlaamsewaterweg.be/
France: Voies navigables de France –VNF	https://www.vnf.fr/vnf/
Germany: Deutsche Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes (WSV)	https://www.gdws.wsv.bund.de/DE/startseite/startseite_node.html
Netherlands: Rijkswaterstaat	https://www.rijkswaterstaat.nl/ https://vaarweginformatie.nl/frp/main/#/home

Water levels/Hydrological Situation		public
Germany:	https://www.pegelonline.wsv.de/gast/start https://www.bafg.de/EN/06_Info_Service/01_WaterLevels/waterlevels_node.html https://www.elwis.de/DE/dynamisch/gewaesserkunde/wasserstaende/	
Europe:	https://www.efas.eu/en/hydrology?field_month_value=01&field_year_value=2023 https://www.eurisportal.eu/hydrometeo/map	

5.2.5 Other Data Sources

Ontology of inland waterway transport system	
Modelling the entity and relations of the IWT domain.	
To be completed in the next phase of the project	
Origin-destination matrix of vessels and barges	
Traffic and transit data about vessels and barges	
To be completed in the next phase of the project	
ST4W	commercial
IWT logistic data	
https://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/st4w-smart-tracking-data-network-for-shipment-by-inland-waterway/	

6 Conclusions and Further steps

The Hazards and Vulnerability Scenario Catalogue presented in this document as well as the building blocks and data sources will serve as the basis for refining or selecting the use cases described in the GA. Based on the evaluation of the stakeholders, a risk analysis will be conducted for the most relevant events. This will be done in the form of a risk matrix for each of the selected events. An example of such a matrix is shown in Figure 6.

Likelihood	Impact			
	None	Low	Medium	High
A - Rare	0	1	2	3
B - Unlikely	0	1	2	3
C - Probable	1	2	3	4
D - Likely	1	2	3	4
E - Certain	1	2	3	4

Figure 6: Simple example of a risk matrix

If necessary, with regard to impact and severity the risk level may be extended to include the "Catastrophic" range. This will be clarified in the further course of the project and discussed with the relevant stakeholders. In this context, the consequences of the events will be analysed in more detail especially with regard to cascading or cumulative effects.

Additionally, a vulnerability analysis will be conducted based on the use cases of the ReNEW project living labs. This analysis will form the basis for the development of a set of strategies on resilience and agility for IWT infrastructures as part of intermodal chains including climate adaptation (medium/long term) and agility (short-term, ad-hoc) measures.

The collection and overview of KPIs for sustainability and resilience created in this document will be further narrowed down and concretized as the project progresses. Some KPIs may be sorted out as irrelevant based on the requirements of the LL. Overall, the LL will select and analyse the KPIs that are most relevant to them and use the results to develop strategies for improving sustainability and resilience. The planned CBA will help evaluate the economic viability of the measures developed in the LL.

Furthermore, in the second version of the deliverable, resilience and sustainability models, simulation libraries, and data sources 2nd Release will be provided, and the first version of strategies will be developed.

7 References

- [1] Blue Glacier, "What is a risk vs threat vs vulnerability?," 2022. <https://blueglacierllc.com/2020/11/what-is-a-risk-vs-threat-vs-vulnerability/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [2] Pentaquard, "The difference between threats and hazards." <https://pentaquard.com.au/the-difference-between-threats-and-hazards/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [3] Risk Steering Committee, "DHS Risk Lexicon," 2010. <https://www.dhs.gov/xlibrary/assets/dhs-risk-lexicon-2010.pdf> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [4] UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, "Hazard." <https://www.undrr.org/terminology/hazard> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [5] United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, "Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030," 2015. <https://www.undrr.org/publication/sendai-framework-disaster-risk-reduction-2015-2030> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [6] United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, "Vulnerability." <https://www.undrr.org/terminology/vulnerability> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [7] E. Dosal, "Top 5 Computer Security Vulnerabilities - Compuquip," 2020. <https://www.compuquip.com/blog/computer-security-vulnerabilities> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [8] International Organization for Standardization, "ISO 31000:2018(en) Risk management – Guidelines," 2018. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:31000:ed-2:v1:en> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [9] R. de L. van Weenen, J. Ferencz, S. Chin, and W. van der Geest, "Living and working conditions in inland navigation in Europe," 297, 2013. [Online]. Available: https://www.ilo.org/sector/Resources/publications/WCMS_234892/lang-en/index.htm
- [10] Nautilus International, "Sustainable inland waterway transport and working conditions: it's time to make a move," 2021. <https://www.nautilusint.org/en/news-insight/telegraph/sustainable-inland-waterway-transport/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [11] E. Tijan, M. Jović, S. Aksentijević, and A. Pucihar, "Digital transformation in the maritime transport sector," Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change, vol. 170, 12087, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120879> .
- [12] Britannica, "strike." <https://www.britannica.com/topic/strike-industrial-relations> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [13] Health and Safety Executive, "Human factors: Managing human failures." <https://www.hse.gov.uk/humanfactors/topics/humanfail.htm> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [14] Cambridge Dictionary, "lockdown." <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/de/worterbuch/englisch/lockdown> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [15] J. Schweighofer, "The impact of extreme weather and climate change on inland waterway transport," Nat. Hazards, vol. 72, pp. 23–40, 2014, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-012-0541-6> .
- [16] F. Vinke, M. van Koningsveld, C. van Dorsser, F. Baart, P. van Gelder, and T. Vellinga, "Cascading effects of sustained low water on inland shipping," Clim. Risk Manag., vol. 35, 100400, 2022.
- [17] L. Liu, Y. Wen, Y. Liang, F. Zhang, and T. Yang, "Extreme Weather Impacts on Inland Waterways Transport of Yangtze River," Atmosphere (Basel), vol. 10, no. 3, 133, 2019.
- [18] ESKP, "Was sind Tornados?" <https://www.eskp.de/grundlagen/naturgefahren/was-sind-tornados-935223/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).

- [19] K. Welch, L. H. Lambert, D. M. Lambert, and P. Kenkel, "Flood-Induced Disruption of an Inland Waterway Transportation System and Regional Economic Impacts," *Water*, vol. 14, no. 5, 753, 2022.
- [20] Die Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes, "Hohe Wasserstände – Auswirkungen auf die Schifffahrt," 2021. Hohe Wasserstände – Auswirkungen auf die Schifffahrt https://www.gdws.wsv.bund.de/SharedDocs/Kurzmeldungen/DE/20210202_Hochwasser_Auswirkungen_Schifffahrt.html (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [21] Cambridge Dictionary, "fog." <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/fog> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [22] Cambridge Dictionary, "earthquake." <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/earthquake> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [23] T. Sugano, A. Nozu, E. Kohama, K. Shimosako, and Y. Kikuchi, "Damage to coastal structures," *Soils Found.*, vol. 54, no. 4, p. Soils Found., 2014.
- [24] M. Searle, "TECTONICS | Mountain Building and Orogeny," in *Encyclopedia of Geology*, Elsevier, 2005, pp. 417–425. doi: 10.1016/B0-12-369396-9/00129-5.
- [25] Understanding Global Change, "Mountain building." <https://ugc.berkeley.edu/background-content/mountain-building/> (accessed Apr. 14, 2023).
- [26] Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, "Einfluss der Eigenschaften der Landschaft auf den Wasserkreislauf," 2013. <http://www.hydrologie.uni-oldenburg.de/ein-bit/12077.html> (accessed Apr. 14, 2023).
- [27] F. Akpan, G. Bendiab, S. Shiaeles, S. Karamperidis, and M. Michaloliakos, "Cybersecurity Challenges in the Maritime Sector," *Network*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 123–138, 2022.
- [28] Ecosystem Valuation, "Workshop on Cybersecurity in Inland Navigation," 2019. https://www.ccr-zkr.org/files/documents/workshops/wrshp050919/04_Vermeir_en.pdf (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [29] X. Liang, S. Fan, J. Lucy, and Z. Yang, "Risk analysis of cargo theft from freight supply chains using a data-driven Bayesian network," *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 226, p. 108702, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.res.2022.108702.
- [30] CloudMask, "Data Breaches: Threats and Consequences." <https://www.cloudmask.com/blog/data-breaches-threats-and-consequences> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [31] European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, "PORT CYBERSECURITY: Good practices for cybersecurity in the maritime sector," 2019. https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/port-cybersecurity-good-practices-for-cybersecurity-in-the-maritime-sector/at_download/fullReport (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [32] "Difference between Kidnap and Hostage." <http://www.differencebetween.info/difference-between-kidnap-and-hostage> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [33] M. Jović, E. Tijan, R. Marx, and B. Gebhard, "Big Data Management in Maritime Transport," *J. Marit. Transp. Sci.*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 123–141, 2019.
- [34] HYPR, "Hybrid Attack." <https://www.hypr.com/security-encyclopedia/hybrid-attack> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [35] J. P. Jenkins, "terrorism," 2023. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/terrorism> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [36] "terrorist attack." <https://www.vocabulary.com/dictionary/terrorist%20attack> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [37] bwl-lexikon.de, "Just-In-Time." <https://www.bwl-lexikon.de/wiki/just-in-time/> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [38] S. Kallada, "What to do if there's dangerous goods spillage on deck," 2017. <https://shashikallada.com/theres-dangerous-goods-spillage-deck/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).

- [39] IWD, "Infrastrukturmängel in Deutschland belasten Unternehmen," 2018. <https://www.iwd.de/artikel/infrastrukturmaengel-in-deutschland-belasten-unternehmen-397286/> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [40] "Top 5 instrumentation problems – and how to avoid them." <https://denca.com/top-5-instrumentation-problems-and-how-to-avoid-them/> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [41] S. M. . Wagner and C. Bode, "Empirische Untersuchung von SC-Risiken und SC-Risikomanagement in Deutschland," in Vahrenkamp, R.; Siepermann, C. (Hrsg.), Risikomanagement in Supply Chains – Gefahren abwehren, Chancen nutzen, Erfolg generieren, 2007, pp. 59–79.
- [42] "The Effects of Protectionism," 2015. <https://www.economicshelp.org/blog/52/trade/effects-protectionism/> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [43] "The economic consequences of increased protectionism," 2017. <https://www.riksbank.se/globalassets/media/rapporter/ppr/fordjupningar/engelska/2017/the-economic-consequences-of-increased-protectionism-article-in-monetary-policy-report-april-2017> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [44] FocusEconomics, "The Economic Effects of Trade Protectionism," 2018. <https://www.focus-economics.com/blog/effects-of-trade-protectionism-on-economy> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [45] CFI, "Economic Conditions," 2023. <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/economics/economic-conditions/> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [46] Economic Policy Institute, "Economic scarring: The long-term impacts of the recession," 2009. <https://www.epi.org/publication/bp243/> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [47] Z. Li, J. Wu, X. Cui, Z. Mi, and L. Peng, "Assessment and influencing factors analysis of economic system vulnerability of the Belt and Road Initiative countries," PLoS One, vol. 17, no. 1, 2022, Accessed: Mar. 09, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8759676/>
- [48] P. Specht, J.-N. Bamler, M. Jović, and N. Meyer-Larsen, "Digital Information Services Needed for a Sustainable Inland Waterway Transportation Business," Sustainability, vol. 14, no. 11, 6392, 2022.
- [49] D. Marchese, E. Reynolds, M. E. Bates, H. Morgan, S. S. Clark, and I. Linkov, "Resilience and sustainability: Similarities and differences in environmental management applications," Sci. Total Environ., vol. 613–614, p. Sci. Total Environ., 2018.
- [50] P. Tamvakis and Y. Xenidis, "Resilience in Transportation Systems," Procedia - Soc. Behav. Sci., vol. 48, p. 3442, 2012.
- [51] A. A. Karl, J. Micheluzzi, L. R. Leite, and C. R. Pereira, "Supply chain resilience and key performance indicators: a systematic literature review," Production, vol. 28, 2018.
- [52] Y. Sheffi and J. B. Rice Jr., "A Supply Chain View of the Resilient Enterprise," MIT Sloan Manag. Rev., vol. 47, no. 1, p. 41, 2005.
- [53] M. J. E. Werner, A. P. Louise, E. G. N. Domingos, L. R. Leite, and C. R. Pereira, "Exploring Organizational Resilience Through Key Performance Indicators," J. Ind. Prod. Eng., vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 51–65, 2021.
- [54] IW-Net Project, "IW-Net Project." <https://www.iw-net.eu/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [55] NSW-Plus, "NSW-Plus - Das erweiterte National Single Window als Basis für eine neue Dienstleistung zur maritimen Prozessoptimierung." <http://www.nsw-plus.de/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [56] E. Tijan, A. Agatić, M. Jović, and S. Aksentijević, "Maritime National Single Window—A Prerequisite for Sustainable Seaport Business," Sustainability, vol. 11, no. 17, 4570, 2019.

- [57] I. Hristov and A. Chirico, "The Role of Sustainability Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in Implementing Sustainable Strategies," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 20, 5742, 2019.
- [58] Indeed Editorial Team, "What Are Safety KPIs? (With Definition and Examples)," 2022. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/what-are-safety-kpis> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [59] Quentic, "Safety KPIs that really matter." <https://www.quentic.com/articles/safety-kpis-that-really-matter/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [60] A. Ali, A. Mahfouz, and A. Arisha, "Analysing Supply Chain Resilience: Integrating the Constructs in a Concept Mapping Framework Via a Systematic Literature Review," *Supply Chang. Manag.*, vol. 22, no. 1, 2017, doi: 10.1108/SCM-06-2016-0197.
- [61] Benoit Racette Services-conseils inc., "Key Performance indicators (KPI) for resilience," 2022. <https://racetteconseils.com/en/key-performance-indicators-kpi-for-resilience/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [62] eCompliance, "Lost Time Injury Frequency Rate (LTIFR): How to Calculate & Reduce It," 2021. <https://www.ecompliance.com/blog/lost-time-injury-frequency-rate/> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [63] M. Christopher and H. Peck, "Building the Resilient Supply Chain," *Int. J. Logist. Manag.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1–14, 2004, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09574090410700275>.
- [64] Q. Zhang, H. Chen, and J. Lu, "Big data analytics in supply chain management: A literature review," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 259, no. 2, pp. 603–620, 2017.
- [65] C. Tozzi, "How to Measure Data Quality – 7 Metrics to Assess the Quality of Your Data," 2022. <https://www.precisely.com/blog/data-quality/how-to-measure-data-quality-7-metrics> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [66] H. J. Kim, C. L. Wu, and B. Ragu-Nathan, "Information sharing and supply chain performance: An empirical investigation," *Int. J. Prod. Econ.*, vol. 140, no. 2, pp. 556–566, 2012.
- [67] M. Jacobson, "Knowledge Sharing Metrics To Determine ROI," 2022. <https://bloomfire.com/blog/knowledge-sharing-metrics/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [68] K. D. Paine, "Guidelines for Measuring Trust in Organizations," 2016. <https://instituteforpr.org/guidelines-for-measuring-trust-in-organizations-2/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [69] SecurityScorecard, "How to Measure Risk Management Performance: KPI & Metrics," 2022. <https://securityscorecard.com/blog/how-to-measure-risk-management-performance> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [70] K. Scholten, P. S. Scott, and B. Fynes, "Mitigation processes – antecedents for building supply chain resilience," *Supply Chain Manag.*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 211–228, 2014.
- [71] Z. Paszkiewicz and W. Picard, "Reference Model for Performance Management in Service-Oriented Virtual Organization Breeding Environments," in Camarinha-Matos, L.M., Paraskakis, I., Afsarmanesh, H. (eds) *Leveraging Knowledge for Innovation in Collaborative Networks. PRO-VE 2009. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology*, vol 307. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg., pp. 505–513. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-04568-4_52.
- [72] M. A. Hariri-Ardebili, S. Sattar, K. Johnson, C. Clavin, J. Fung, and L. Ceferino, "A Perspective towards Multi-Hazard Resilient Systems: Natural Hazards and Pandemics," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 8, 4508, 2022.
- [73] P. Bocchini, D. Frangopol, T. Ummenhofer, and T. Zinke, "Resilience and Sustainability of Civil Infrastructure: Toward a Unified Approach," *J. Infrastruct. Syst.*, vol. 20, no. 2, 2014.
- [74] Shipping KPIs, "Overview." <https://www.shipping-kpi.org/book/pages/concepts#?kpiProfileId=22> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).

- [75] BIMCO, "BIMCO Shipping KPIs." <https://www.bimco.org/ships-ports-and-voyage-planning/shipping-kpi-system> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [76] European Commission, "Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis of Investment Projects," 2014. <https://iwlearn.net/resolveuid/719db343-4025-45dc-9e6f-541a2d43e482> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [77] General Economics Division, "DEVELOPMENT PROJECT PROFORMA/PROPOSAL (DPP) MANUAL (Instructions for Preparing Development Project Proposal) Part- 2: Appendixes," 2014. https://oldweb.lged.gov.bd/UploadedDocument/UnitPublication/1/313/16-B_DPP-Manual-Part-2.pdf (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [78] D. E. Mazarakos, F. Andritsos, and V. Kostopoulos, "Recovery of oil-pollutant from shipwrecks: DIFIS project," *Int. J. Struct. Integr.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 285–319, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.1108/17579861211264398.
- [79] "Kosten-Nutzen-Analyse." http://www.daswirtschaftslexikon.com/d/kosten_nutzen_analyse/kosten_nutzen_analyse.htm (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [80] Asian Development Bank, "Cost-Benefit analysis for development, A Practical Guide," 2013. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/institutional-document/33788/files/cost-benefit-analysis-development.pdf> (accessed Mar. 09, 2023).
- [81] M. Elliott, Partners Ltd., and Economics for the Environment Consultancy LTD., "Study on the valuation and restoration of biodiversity damage for the purpose of environmental liability, Final Report," 2001.
- [82] "Final Report Summary - DIFIS (Double Inverted Funnel for Intervention on Ship-Wrecks)," 2011. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/516360/reporting/pl> (accessed Apr. 14, 2023).
- [83] FOREST EUROPE, "Market price method," 2018. https://foresteurope.org/fe_fes_method/market-price-method/ (accessed Mar. 08, 2023).
- [84] Ecosystem Valuation, "Dollar-based Ecosystem Valuation Methods." https://www.ecosystemvaluation.org/dollar_based.htm (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [85] Ecosystem Valuation, "Methods, Section 2: Productivity Methods." <https://www.ecosystemvaluation.org/productivity.htm> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [86] Ecosystem Valuation, "Methods, Section 3: Hedonic Pricing Method." https://www.ecosystemvaluation.org/hedonic_pricing.htm%0A%0A (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [87] Ecosystem Valuation, "Methods, Section 4: Travel Cost Method." https://www.ecosystemvaluation.org/travel_costs.htm%0A%0A (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [88] Ecosystem Valuation, "Methods, Section 5: Damage Cost Avoided, Replacement Cost, and Substitute Cost Methods." https://www.ecosystemvaluation.org/cost_avoided.htm (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [89] Ecosystem Valuation, "Methods, Section 6: Contingent Valuation Method." https://www.ecosystemvaluation.org/contingent_valuation.htm%0A%0A (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [90] Datarails, "Internal Rate of Return." <https://www.datarails.com/finance-glossary/internal-rate-of-return/> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [91] "Amortisationsrechnung." <https://welt-der-bwl.de/Amortisationsrechnung> (accessed Mar. 06, 2023).
- [92] "RIS COMEX." <https://www.riscomex.eu/> (accessed Mar. 14, 2023).